

Walk21 Ireland 2022 Conference Report

T
DUBLIN
OLLSCOIL TEICNEOLAÍOCHTA
BHAILE ÁTHA CLIATH
TECHNOLOGICAL
UNIVERSITY DUBLIN

WALK 21
IRELAND

THE DECADE TO CHANGE

Steps to Deliver the 2030 Agenda
for Sustainable Development

OCTOBER 2023

Rialtas na hÉireann
Government of Ireland

An Roinn Sláinte
Department of Health

An Roinn Turasóireachta, Cultúir, Ealaíon, Gaeltachta, Spóirt agus Meán
Department of Tourism, Culture, Arts, Gaeltacht, Sport and Media

An Roinn Iompair
Department of Transport

SPÓRT ÉIREANN
SPORT IRELAND

CONTENTS

Introduction	6	Plenary 5 – Closing Plenary: Walking purposefully through the decade for change.....	68
Walk21 Foundation	6	Walkshops	70
Conference Background	6	Parallel, Roundtable and Poster Sessions	72
Walk21 Ireland Event Overview	8	Social Events	74
Precursor Events – The Irish Story	10	National Events	75
Funding Commitment	14	Post Conference Review and Reflections	78
The Handover	14	Communications	78
Conference Organisation	14	Funding and Spend	82
People	16	Conference Conclusions	84
Steering Committee	18	Reflections from TU Dublin	88
Delivery Team	18	Legacy Projects Update	90
Programme Committee and International Review Team	19	Appendix A – The Business Case for Walk21 Ireland	92
Local Advisory Council	22	Appendix B – Committees and Partners	96
Global and Local Challenges During Project Delivery.....	24	Walk21 Steering Committee	96
The Brand	26	Walk21 Advisory Committee	97
Sponsorship and Ethical Considerations	26	Walk21 Programme Committee	98
Communications	27	Walk21 International Review Committee	98
The Grangegorman campus Venue	28	Walk21 Ireland Delivery Team	99
Local Community and Campus Engagement	30	Appendix C – Parallel Sessions, Walkshops, Roundtables and Posters	100
Health and Safety Assessment	31	Parallel Sessions	100
Conference Merchandise and Sustainability Decisions	32	Walkshops	116
Accessibility	34	Roundtables	118
Recognition of Learning	34	Posters	119
The Call for Contributions	36	Appendix D: World Café Consolidation	124
Monitoring and Evaluation	38	Safety	124
The Conference Event	40	Equity	125
Attendance	40	Gender	126
Youth Forum	42	Appendix E: Conference Feedback	128
Pre-conference Workshops	46		
Opening Ceremony	50		
Plenary 1 - Global Perspectives, National Commitment, Local Action:.....	52		
Plenary 2 - Walking as the foundation for healthy bodies, minds and streets	54		
Plenary 3 - Ensuring equity and access for everyone	56		
Plenary 4 - Building for Walking: hard yards or easy street?	60		
World Café - How can we make walking safer.. to help deliver SDGs by 2030?.....	62		

Introduction

This section will detail the background of the conference and how it came to Ireland. It will give context to the event as well as its position of influence on the global stage.

Walk21 Foundation

The [Walk21 Foundation](#), known as Walk21, is a global organisation that supports every person's right to walk in a safe, inclusive and welcoming environment by providing evidence, tools, training, and accreditation to a global network of concerned communities, politicians, academics, and practitioners. [Their goal](#) is to ensure that “walking is measured, valued and appropriately provided for so that everyone in the world can choose to walk and enjoy the experience”.

Conference Background

The Walk21 Conference, the global walking summit, started in 2000 with a conference in London at the end of a European LIFE¹-funded project. An international community was inspired to meet annually to discuss research, policy, practice, and innovation on walking and walkable communities and cities. It has taken place all over the world from Hong Kong to Bogota, and Rotterdam to Sydney.

In 2022, for the first time, the international conference had a national focus rather than a city focus. The 22nd Walk21 conference, themed 'The Decade to Change', was hosted by Technological University Dublin in partnership with three government departments: The Department of Health, the Department of Tourism, Culture, Arts, Gaeltacht, Sport and Media through their national agency Sport Ireland, and the Department of Transport.

¹[Programme for Environment and Climate Action \(LIFE\) | European Commission \(europa.eu\)](#)

Walk21 Ireland Event Overview

The conference took place in multiple locations around Ireland over five days from 19-23 September 2022. The dates for the conference were chosen in line with European Mobility Week and National Walking Week, both of which lead into the Irish National Walking Day (Sunday, 25 September 2022). This day also kicked off the European Week of Sport.

The conference highlighted and discussed current and new practices in policy making, urban planning, mobility and transport planning, as well as the impacts and benefits of walking on community, climate change, safety and health. The conference also involved an extensive social programme of activities for attending delegates including a welcome reception, a conference dinner and other networking opportunities. This gave delegates the chance to get to know each other or reconnect, and to discuss research, work and practices relevant to the themes of the conference. As the conference had not been held in person since 2019, social events were very well attended and enjoyed.

The conference commenced on Monday 19 September between two locations in Dublin's City Centre. The Youth Forum took place at the EPIC Museum, CHQ Building, Dublin 1, along with the evening welcome reception and most of the pre-conference workshops. On the same day the THE PEP Consortium Meeting was held at TU Dublin. TU Dublin's Grangegorman campus was the main location for the conference, with all plenary and parallel sessions held in the East Quad between Tuesday 20-22 September. This central location was also the starting point for 'walkshops' held around the City. Satellite events took place in Galway, Limerick, and Cork cities on Friday 23 September while TU Dublin hosted sessions several international delegations who combined their network meetings with the conference.

The target groups for the conference were international and domestic communities of practice involved in walking and disciplines related to walking, including designers, policy makers, advocates or those promoting walking.

Walk21 Ireland - Conference Impact Figures

5

day conference
with events & activities
scheduled daily

1,197

conference attendees
406 in-person
& 791 virtual

42

speakers from 42 countries
& across all continents
participated in the conference

100

students aged 10-18 from
schools in Ireland participated
in the Youth Forum on Walking

8

pre-conference workshops
hosted by TU Dublin &
partner stakeholders

130+

conference contributions

7

call-to-action recommendations
presented by the Youth Forum at
the conference opening plenary

29

conference sessions

Neutral space

TU Dublin acted as a neutral space
to host the conference
for interdisciplinary
collaboration & open discussion

3

Government of Ireland
departments support
Walk21 Ireland with funding

Committees

Four Government of Ireland
departments, 9 state agencies & NGOs
sit on conference committees

4

satellite conference events
engage participants nationally

5

professional organisations
allocate CPD accreditations
to conference participation

4 sub themes

address conference theme: 'The
Decade to Change – Steps to
Deliver the 2030 Agenda
for Sustainable Development'

10

'Early Career Researcher'
scholarships for countries
in the Global South

12

walkshops; a unique
applied learning & knowledge
exchange opportunity putting
theory into practice

Precursor Events – The Irish Story

Inspired by their participation at previous Walk21 Conferences, TU Dublin's Dr Lorraine D'Arcy, Health Service Executive's (HSE) Dr Michelle Hardie-Murphy, and Get Ireland Walking's Jason King and Dr Emer O'Leary, approached the Walk21 Foundation at the 2018 Bogotá conference to express an interest in bringing the Walk21 Conference to Ireland. The vision for the conference was for an interdisciplinary approach bringing transport, planning, health and physical activity promotion and other associated professions together to deliver on walking and walkability in Ireland.

Figure 1: Graphic representation of the discussions at the Get Ireland Walking Event

An Irish working group was formed in June 2019 after discussions with key stakeholders. The group had representation from a variety of governmental departments, state agencies, academia and advocacy groups. It was considered that an academic institution could provide a neutral space for the conference and it was agreed that TU Dublin would be the lead agency. This space ensured that no discipline area or group could be perceived to be more important than others.

On Friday 07 February 2020, a diverse group of 60 stakeholders joined the 'Get Ireland Walking - Stakeholder Forum on All Purpose Walking in Ireland - Working Towards the Future' event at TU Dublin. The day-long workshop had three strategic objectives:

1. To better connect the ecosystem seeking to encourage more walking in Ireland, whilst drawing out the supports and infrastructure needed to develop it.
2. To co-develop recommendations for a National Walking Strategy.
3. To agree a high-level action plan going forward to create a connection with Walk21 and the bid process.

Figure 2: Key Walk21 Ireland Stakeholders pictured at the Get Ireland Walking Event in TU Dublin February 2020

²Get-Ireland-Walking_Report_Connect-the-Dots.pdf (getirelandwalking.ie)

Key recommendations made for the Walk21 Ireland conference planning included²:

- Giving consideration to ensure the overall conference feels coherent.
- Ensure that Walk21 is used as an opportunity to engage with critical issues today including emphasising the role of walking in addressing climate, sustainable development, and environmental transitions; walking as a tool to bridge Ireland's urban - rural divide; and social prescribing and walking for better health and mental health outcomes.
- There was a strong consensus from the conference working group that the event must achieve nationwide visibility and be potentially staged across multiple locations recognising that Ireland is "big enough to matter, and small enough to include everyone".
- Walk21 should be used as an opportunity to pilot something practical to inform and change the debate around walking.
- Be an opportunity for learning, education and exchange and to showcase real-world case studies on topics that are useful to them and key stakeholder groups, such as planners, retailers, and the business community..
- Make walking a creative feature of the conference.
- Use Walk21 as an opportunity to catalyse place-based and/or community-led innovation.
- Using creative approaches to capture the main outputs of the conference.
- Stakeholders outlined several areas they hoped Walk21 could create a lasting legacy for walking in Ireland. This spanned from Walk21 feeding into the development and launch of a National Walking Strategy; That it places walking on the political agenda and in turn inform future policy; That the built environment / infrastructure for walking is vastly improved; That there is increased funding allocations and budgeting commitments for walking; Ireland recognised internationally as a walking country / destination.
- Getting community engagement and involvement at the conference. To ensure good public engagement in developing and delivering the conference.

Funding Commitment

Informed by the outcomes of the Get Ireland Walking event and initial conversations with the group of stakeholders brought together by the conference lead, a funding case was made by TU Dublin to government ministers which outlined the relevance of the conference to government policies (Appendix A). Three government departments, The Department of Health, the Department of Tourism, Culture, Arts, Gaeltacht, Sport through their national agency Sport Ireland, and the Department of Transport agreed to commit €250,000 each to the running of the conference. This amount was based on information shared with the team from the last European Walk21 conference in Rotterdam in 2018 and the VeloCity cycling conference held in Dublin in 2019. It was also acknowledged that TU Dublin's in-kind contributions of venues and staff time contributed a significant value to delivering the conference and minimising project costs.

The Handover

Walk21 Seoul was held virtually in May 2021 and TU Dublin President Prof. David FitzPatrick accepted the handover from the City of Seoul. He was presented with a pair of ornate traditional shoes and the blessing 'may your path be lined with flowers'. As a nod to this gesture, the pathways outside the East Quad building on the TU Dublin Grangegorman campus were decorated with flowers for the Walk21 Ireland event.

Conference Organisation

Building upon the discussions at the Get Ireland Walking event in February 2020 and informed by Walk21's experience from previous events, a partnership approach between TU Dublin and Walk21 International was taken for the delivery of the Walk21 Ireland conference. TU Dublin took on the role of lead local agency sponsor, and conference host. This involved

being the key contact for the Walk21 team in Ireland and supporting the delivery of the event through collaboration with other agencies and to act as fund holder and administrator. Walk21 International's role involved strategic input, programme management, oversight, monitoring and support from their team on all aspects of the event. Walk21 International also contracted a local conference coordinator to be responsible for the management and delivery of the event.

The conference organisation structure was developed with five main pillars - the Steering Committee, the Delivery Team, the Programme Committee, the International Review Committee and the Local Advisory Council.

Figure 3: TU Dublin receiving the conference handover from the City of Seoul

People

Michael Ahern
Head of Transport Development
National Transport Authority

Jennifer Boyer
Vice President for Sustainability
TU Dublin

Dr Úna Beagon
Head of Civil Engineering
TU Dublin

Paul Brosnan
Health & Wellbeing Programme
Department of Health

Louise Burke
Director of Participation
Sport Ireland

Dr Jackie Bourke
Urban Geographer
Ireland

Rachel Cahill
Director of Executive Office & Sustainability Lead
Transport Infrastructure Ireland

Anne Campion
Executive Assistant to the VP for Sustainability
TU Dublin

Deirdre Donohue
National Roads, Greenways, and Active Travel Division
Department of Transport

Dr Lorraine D'Arcy
Sustainability Action Research & Innovation Lead
TU Dublin

Christina Duff
Schools Wellbeing (Physical Activity & Health Literacy)
Irish Heart Foundation

Léon Fox
Higher Executive Officer
Department of Rural & Community Affairs

Dr David Gaul
Sports Management & Physical Activity Lecturer
TU Dublin

Dr Michelle Hardie Murphy
Senior Health Promotion & Improvement Officer
Health Services Executive

Alison Harvey
Planning Programmes/ Policy Manager
The Heritage Council

Christine Hegarty
Road Safety Education Manager
Road Safety Authority

Kathleen Jacobi
Sustainability Portfolio Co-Ordinator
Transport Infrastructure Ireland

Jason King
Programme Manager
Get Ireland Walking

James Lavelle
Assistant Principal Officer
Department of Tourism, Culture, Arts, Gaeltacht, Sport & Media

Prof. Kevin Leyden
Professor of Political Science
University of Galway

Dr Madeleine Lyes
Chair
Limerick Pedestrian Network

Dr Fiona Mansergh
Assistant Principal Officer
Department of Health

Antonia Martin
Active Travel Communication, Engagement & Promotion Manager
Dublin City Council

Ciara Munnely
Outdoor Recreation Manager
Sport Ireland

Sarah O'Brien
National Lead, Healthy Eating Active Living Programme
Health Services Executive

David O'Connor
Head of Environment & Planning
TU Dublin

Gabriel O'Gorman
Department of Tourism, Culture, Arts, Gaeltacht, Sport

Derek O'Neill (RIP)
National Roads, Greenways, and Active Travel Division
Department of Transport

Ruth C O'Reilly
Senior Built Environment Design Advisor
National Disability Authority

Ian Smith
Department of Tourism, Culture, Arts, Gaeltacht, Sport and Media

Sarah Taylor
National Roads, Greenways, and Active Travel Division
Department of Transport

Bronwen Thornton
CEO
Walk21

Jim Walker
Director
Walk21

Steering Committee

The Steering Committee was the core decision making committee chaired by Jennifer Boyer, Vice President for Sustainability at TU Dublin. The committee consisted of representatives from Walk21, TU Dublin, and the three funding government departments; Department of Health, Department of Tourism, Culture, Arts, Gaeltacht, Sport and Media, Department of Transport and Sport Ireland.

The committee met monthly in the year up to the conference to provide oversight to the conference planning. Further details of committees are outlined in Appendix B.

Delivery Team

The Delivery Team was the core organising group for the conference and was made up of staff from Walk21 and TU Dublin, with inputs from some external contractors, listed in Appendix B.

Walk21 Steering Committee Members:

Jennifer Boyer (Chair) – TU Dublin
Anne Champion (Secretariat) – TU Dublin
Dr Lorraine D’Arcy – TU Dublin
Paul Brosnan – Department of Health
Louise Burke – Sport Ireland
Deirdre Donohue – Department of Transport
James Lavelle – Department of Tourism, Culture, Arts, Gaeltacht, Sport and Media
Dr Fiona Mansergh – Department of Health
Gabriel O’Gorman – Department of Tourism, Culture, Arts, Gaeltacht, Sport and Media
Derek O’Neill – Department of Transport
Ian Smith – Department of Tourism, Culture, Arts, Gaeltacht, Sport and Media
Bronwen Thornton – Walk21
Jim Walker – Walk21

Walk21 Delivery Team Members:

Jennifer Boyer – TU Dublin
Anne Champion – TU Dublin
Clare Connell
Dr Lorraine D’Arcy – TU Dublin (Conference Chair)
Rebecca Flanagan – TU Dublin
Ailish Lally – Walk21 (Conference Coordinator)
Éadaoin Ryan – TU Dublin
Bronwen Thornton – Walk21
Ralf Tinga – Walk21
Jim Walker – Walk21

Programme Committee and International Review Team

The Walk21 Ireland programme committee comprised of academics from different disciplines plus practitioners to reflect the interdisciplinary programme. All programme committee members read all 275 valid abstracts and in conjunction with the international review team's feedback inputted into the final programme design.

Walk21 Programme Committee Members:

Dr Úna Beagon – TU Dublin, Head of Civil Engineering

Dr Lorraine D'Arcy – TU Dublin, Sustainability Action Research

& Innovation Lead

Dr David Gaul – TU Dublin, Lecturer in Sports Management and

Physical Activity

Jason King – Get Ireland Walking, Programme Manager

David O'Connor – TU Dublin, Head of Environment and

Planning

Bronwen Thornton – Walk21, CEO

Jim Walker – Walk21, Director

Figure 4: Walk21 Ireland Conference Organisation Structure

The International Review Committee comprised of 39 academics and professionals from around the world (listed in Appendix B). This diverse group provided academic rigour to the submissions that chose to be reviewed academically and also a practical implementation and/or policy relevance lens depending on the theme selected by the applicants. The academic option can be an important requisite for academics to access to funding to attend conferences.

Local Advisory Council

The Local Advisory Council was made up of key people from Irish organisations to guide and advise the conference design to ensure relevance to their sectors, and to also disseminate information about the conference through their networks. This group also got involved in session chairing and other roles at the conference.

Walk21 Local Advisory Council Members:

Michael Ahearn – National Transport Authority

Dr Jackie Bourke – Urban Geographer

Rachel Cahill – Transport Infrastructure Ireland

Christina Duff – Irish Heart Foundation

Leon Fox – Department of Rural and Community Affairs

Dr Michelle Hardie Murphy – Health Services Executive

Alison Harvey – Heritage Council

Christine Hegarty – Road Safety Authority

Kathleen Jacobi – Transport Infrastructure Ireland

Jason King – Get Ireland Walking

Prof. Kevin Leyden – NUI Galway

Dr Madeleine Lyes – Irish Pedestrian Network

Antonia Martin – Dublin City Council

Ciara Munnely – Sport Ireland

Sarah O'Brien – Health Services Executive

Ruth C O'Reilly – National Disability Authority

Dr Lorraine D'Arcy (Chair) – TU Dublin

Global and Local Challenges During Project Delivery:

There were many global and local challenges which evolved between the approach made to Walk21 to host the conference in Ireland in 2018 and the delivery of the conference in 2022.

Due considerations needed to be given to the global context of a climate emergency, a pandemic, a war and associated immigrant crisis and visa difficulties, global equity and need, whilst also delivering an accessible and inclusive event. The Walk21 Seoul conference moved to a fully virtual conference following its initial postponement to May 2021. The accessibility of the online content was welcomed particularly from lower income countries for whom international travel can be a barrier to participation. The Walk21 Ireland delivery team were conscious of this in the knowledge that the conference was being handed over to an African nation. Setting up a high-quality system to access the conference online also gave the option to move fully online if the need arose. From a sustainability and gender, equity and inclusion perspective the online option allowed those that did not wish to fly, or who could not travel due to caring or other responsibilities, to still attend the global conversation.

Gender and inclusion checks were consistently made when reviewing the makeup of working groups and conference sessions. Irish disability and minority groups, such as the National Disability Authority and Pavee Point who represent Irish Traveller communities, were invited to submit abstracts and the conference delivery team engaged with them to ensure that any barriers to their participation were overcome.

The Brand

The Walk21 Ireland branding was developed by Trish Fox Designs and symbolised the connections of pathways both the relationships within walking related disciplines on the island of Ireland and the physical paths that connect us. The Walk21 International logo with its circle was incorporated into the Walk21 Ireland logo design. The Walk21 Ireland logo will be reworked post conference to be used for Walk21 Ireland legacy projects. The event company for Walk21 Ireland, Catapult Events, made excellent use of the branding throughout the in person and online staging of the event.

Figure 5: Walk21 Ireland Conference branding and decoration

Sponsorship and Ethical Considerations

As an interdisciplinary event, when potential sponsorship opportunities were discussed, a frank discussion was had about what ethical considerations should be given to potential sponsors. Each of the funding government departments had specific guidelines on brands that should not be considered. For example, fast or high calorie food brands, vaping or alcohol (health), gambling

(sport), or car companies (active travel/ transport). Given the generous contributions from the Government departments it was agreed that sponsorship would only be sought for specific purposes. The sponsorships received were:

- Dublin City Council sponsored the Opening Reception and the Youth Forum
- Fingal County Council sponsored the World Café (which was to be held in their county but had to be moved as the venue was required for an international emergency response)
- DBFL Consulting Engineers, Galway City Council and VREF³ (the Volvo Research and Educational Foundation) contributed to plenary speaker costs.
- VREF also sponsored 10 International Researcher Bursaries for early career researchers from low- and middle-income countries.

Communications

Targeted audiences for conference communications were both national and international. Walk21 International utilised its social media platform and mailing lists to reach out to its international community. To achieve the transdisciplinary participation envisaged by the steering committee and local advisory group while also engaging in good practice of not soliciting and compliance with data protection legislation, the delivery team generated a local list of stakeholders with the help of the committees. Walkability researchers in TU Dublin also shared relevant contacts with the delivery team. Social media posts and notifications were regularly shared by many of the national organisations on the advisory team which was greatly appreciated.

Alice PR provided support to promote the conference in the weeks leading up to the conference. Claire Connell supported the conference delivery in the early stages of conference promotion engaging with stakeholder groups and their communications teams. In particular, Claire's experience was invaluable in the organisation of our campus walk event in April 2022 to promote the conference. TU Dublin and Walk21's communications and PR team also provided vital support leading up to and during the conference.

³ While VREF are linked to a car company in name, assurances were made that the organisation is a philanthropic one that uses historic profits to fund projects in sustainable and equitable mobility. This sponsorship was approved by the steering committee.

The Grangegorman Venue

The main venue for the Walk21 conference was the East Quad building located on TU Dublin's Grangegorman campus. The Grangegorman campus is an award-winning example of adaptive reuse, with the former St. Brendan's Hospital buildings on the campus retrofitted to meet the requirements of the modern university. The Grangegorman campus is an exemplar of urban regeneration. It is a unique place within the northern inner city redeveloped to bring the life blood of the city, its people, into and through a previously impermeable part of the city and beyond once again. The work undertaken at the campus is an example of how by increasing the filtered permeability of not just historic institutional lands enables us meet our climate goals and to improve the health and wellbeing of the people that use these spaces. Campus tours were given to conference participants during the conference alongside 'walkshops' covering topics such as the history and biodiversity of the site.

The campus was easily accessible to national and international attendees via public transport using the Green and Red Luas lines, national rail stations and a number of Dublin and national bus routes. The campus is also highly accessible by bicycle with a Dublin Bike stand located beside the East Quad venue, along with high levels of walkability to and around the campus.

Several other venues from around the city including the EPIC Museum, the Round Room at the Mansion House and Linen Hall were used to host Walk21 events. Walkshops and Workshops were also hosted in Limerick and Cork with partners from the Irish Pedestrian Network, Cork City Council and Get Ireland Walking.

Catering for Walk21 was primarily supplied by local suppliers Kennedy's and Irish Country Markets, including one food truck run by a TU Dublin culinary arts graduate. The Walk21 Conference Dinner was hosted at The Round Room at the Mansion House.

Local Community and Campus Engagement

The conference steering committee and local advisory group were very supportive of TU Dublin's wish to engage staff, students and local community groups as much as possible with the event. This was done through a number of initiatives.

The Walk21 Ireland Conference was launched on 28th April 2022 on the TU Dublin Grangegorman Campus. Minister of State for Public Health and Wellbeing, Frank Feighan T.D, joined with school children from the Dublin 7 Educate Together National Primary School, and TU Dublin staff and students, to launch the conference and take an enjoyable walk together around the campus. A [video](#) created from the launch can be viewed by clicking the image below.

During the conference TU Dublin promoted our new campus which showcases best practice walkability and new state of the art performance spaces. Our student musicians performed at lunchtimes and the TU Dublin harp ensemble welcomed guests to the conference dinner. One of the lunchtime food trucks belongs to a TU Dublin culinary arts graduate and our sustainable transport and health researchers, students and staff volunteered their time helping at the conference. Lunchtime food on campus was set up with food trucks and a covered lunch space on campus to allow integration with campus life.

In addition to the TU Dublin volunteers, opportunities to contribute and participate were given to local community and advocacy groups to volunteer at the conference in exchange for their conference registration. This was greatly appreciated by these groups who have limited funds available to them. Anyone who wished to volunteer within the TU Dublin community was asked to provide information, such as availability during the conference and contact details, via a Microsoft Form, which was then used to create a schedule for volunteer work throughout the week. This help was essential to support the conference and the organisers.

Health and Safety Assessment

A detailed risk assessment was compiled, with the guidance of TU Dublin's Health and Safety team. This outlined any potential safety risks surrounding the conference, as well as the measures put in place to mitigate them. It involved considering all venues and events across the conference, both on and off the TU Dublin campus. Assembly points for emergencies were identified for each venue, as well as the location of defibrillators on the campus, and staff with first aid training. After some initial adjustments, the assessment was approved by the University's Health and Safety, Estates, and Insurance team. The events management company, Catapult, provided their own risk assessment in their event management plan, which detailed risks and mitigating measures related to their work, and their contactors' work, around staging, installing set designs and the stretch tent used on the campus. Extra

overnight security professionals were brought in to secure the stretch tent on the TU Dublin campus at night, which was being used to provide a space for lunch during the day. Children who took part in the Youth Forum were required to provide consent for in order to attend and were supervised at all times by their teachers.

Conference Merchandise and Sustainability Decisions

All procurement and conference merchandise decisions were made with sustainability in mind. Local supplier Klee Paper provided sustainable branded items such as notebooks made from recycled paper, pens made from plants, and thermal steel mugs, all made in Europe with conference branding on them. Another local supplier, Tara Slevin Group, provided drinking bottles, BPA free and made from recycled polyethylene terephthalate, with conference branding on them, for members of the Youth Forum. Conference merchandise was kept to a minimum, with only items that were considered genuinely useful or helpful purchased, to avoid waste. Instead of giving each delegate a bag of merchandise it was offered at the registration desk if people wanted to avail of it. Lanyards were made with recycled cotton. Detailed conference programmes were not printed but instead a QR code was printed on the lanyard.

For catering on campus, local procurement and sustainable options were a key consideration. Vegan options and dairy free milks were available at all lunch and coffee breaks. All plates and cutlery were compostable which also minimised waste management planning. All foods provided adhered to Healthy Campus guidance⁴ and Green-Campus⁵ principles.

Accessibility

Consideration was given to accessibility by broadcasting the conference live, so that the event could be attended both online as well as in-person, allowing more people to take part in the conference. The sites of the conference talks and Youth Forum/Welcome Reception were also accessible by wheelchair, and a quiet room was provided in TU Dublin's East Quad building if people needed somewhere to take a break from the activity of the conference or to breastfeed. The food provided included accommodations for those with intolerances and allergies.

Recognition of Learning

Continuous Professional Development (CPD) accreditation for the event was obtained from the following professional organisations:

- Royal Institute of the Architects of Ireland
- Engineers Ireland
- Transport Planning Society
- Chartered Institute of Highways and Transportation (CIHT)
- Irish Society of Chartered Physiotherapists

Figure 6: Professional CPD Accreditations for Walk21 Ireland

⁴<https://hea.ie/policy/health-and-wellbeing-landing-page/healthy-campus-landing-page/healthy-campus-charter-and-framework/>

⁵<https://www.greencampusireland.org/about/>

The Call for Contributions

Following a process of consultation with the conference committees and informed by the Get Ireland Walking 2020 event's report, the overall conference theme of *'The Decade to Change – Steps to Deliver the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development'* and sub-themes were agreed and circulated in the call for contributions. They were:

1. Evidence based walking actions

TU Dublin is supporting the Government of Ireland by conducting research, collecting local data and providing expert training for staff to improve the effectiveness and impact of walking policy. Civil engineers, transport planners, architects and urban designers are in collaboration with academics. Contributions are invited that share relevant walking research, data collection and training system that are increasing knowledge, skills and building capacity for delivering actions for people walking.

2. Active places for people

Streetscape improvements and networks of walking trails in both rural and urban areas are being developed by Sport Ireland to connect more people with quality infrastructure and support healthy lifestyles.

Contributions are invited that demonstrate how places have been transformed to support and encourage more walking and the impact that has had on the quality of life all year round.

3. Targeting those that walk the most

Encouraging more people to walk more often is a common goal. Understanding the different walking needs of women, children, the elderly, people on low incomes and those with disabilities in particular is helping the Government of Ireland to ensure their policy and investment decisions are inclusive and responsive.

Contributions are invited that share how citizens have been engaged, different needs identified from different groups, and investments in walkability tailored in response.

4. The Decade for Change

One of the first national campaigns – 'Get Ireland Walking' has, for several years, promoted and celebrated the positive outcomes of people walking. Increasingly walking is being valued and measured as integral to addressing the climate emergency and delivering the Sustainable Development Goal commitments.

Contributions are invited that share how walking is being valued, invested in, and monitored, especially in relation to SDG's. This could include examples of walking in road danger reduction plans, Nationally Determined Contributions, or more accessible public transport.

Figure 7: The Call for Contributions

Monitoring and Evaluation

A Walk21 Ireland evaluation survey was circulated to attendees after the event and 169 responses were received over 11 days from 27 September to 7 October 2022. The survey was sent to all who registered to attend in person or for the immersive virtual experience. Just over 80% of respondents attended the conference in person. Respondents are mainly from Europe and, probably unsurprisingly, almost one quarter are from Ireland. They represented all age groups with roughly 50% are under 44 years of age.

3. How did you attend the conference?

Figure 8: How respondents attended the conference

42. Which country are you from?

Figure 9: Where survey respondents were from

Feedback from respondents was positive. Overall, delegates found the conference enjoyable, engaging and informative. Of the three organised social events, delegates reported having enjoyed them, especially non-Irish delegates. Respondents reported being extremely happy with networking opportunities at the conference with 60% scoring it 9 or 10 out of 10. Specific feedback on each session is described in Appendix E.

Figure 10: Wordcloud of how respondents summarised the conference

The Conference Event

This section contains an overview of the key events at the conference which ran from 19-23 September, 2022.

Attendance

The anticipated attendance for the conference was c. 650 in person attendees, with 70% coming from Ireland and 30% international (predominantly European and North American). Given the conference’s relevance to policy, practice and research the anticipated mix of professions is outlined in figure 16. The anticipated virtual attendance was c. 1,000 with 30% Irish virtual delegates and 70% International virtual delegates. **The actual in person attendance for the event was 406** with 55.5% Irish delegates and 44.5% International delegates. Attendees and speakers came from 42 countries and from across all continents.

TARGET AUDIENCES - IN-PERSON CONFERENCE

Figure 11: The projected breakdown of conference attendees

The virtual attendance was 791 person. Of these, 595 people or 75%, were via the Walk21 YouTube channel (free to access plenary sessions only) and the rest, 196 or 25%, were via the paid Hopin platform. Like the in-person attendees, the virtual attendance was representative of all continents.

All parallel sessions, except for ‘walkshops’, were broadcast through virtual event platform, Hopin at a cost of €50 to the delegate. As well as this, all in-person registrants were given access to the Hopin platform as part of their ticket to enable greater access to content for those who could not attend all sessions in person.

Youth Forum

From the start of the planning process for Walk21 Ireland there was a clear ambition to ensure that young people's voices were clearly heard at the event.

On Monday 19 September, at the EPIC Museum in Dublin, over 100 Irish youth between the ages of 10 and 18 participated in the Youth Forum on Walking sponsored by Dublin City Council. The forum was opened by Lord Mayor Caroline Conroy and facilitated by Dr Clíodhna Martin from the Marino Institute of Education and Dr Lorraine D'Arcy from TU Dublin with group moderators from the Walk21 Advisory Committee and TU Dublin staff and PhD researchers.

Figure 12: The Youth Forum at the EPIC Museum

Walk21 Youth Forum - Call-to-Action

Over 100 students aged between 10 - 18 years old and from schools across Ireland participated in the Walk21 Youth Forum on Walking. Students from the Dublin 7 Educate Together National School presented the call to action to the conference opening plenary and amongst the many great suggestions the key actions included:

Better, wider and more footpaths

More shortcuts

Better lighting

Educating boys around women's safety fears and harassment

More enforcement of traffic speeds

Parking on footpaths and design for safety

Finally, they want places to go and safe places to hang out

Figure 13: The Youth Forum Call-to-Action

Students from the Dublin 7 Educate Together National School presented the call to action to the opening conference plenary and amongst the many great suggestions the key actions included:

- better, wider and more footpaths,
- more shortcuts,
- better lighting,
- educating boys around women's safety fears and harassment,
- more enforcement of traffic speeds,
- parking on footpaths and design for safety,
- finally, they want places to go and safe places to hang out.

Feedback from students/teachers who attended the Youth Forum:

"On behalf of our school, TY teachers and students we would just like to extend our deepest appreciation in being invited to the Walk 21 conference with you in the Epic Museum. Our students were thrilled to be asked and really enjoyed their day with you - they loved participating and being part of a beautiful group set in a positive atmosphere. Lunch was delicious and incredibly kind of you."

"Many thanks for thinking of us and allowing us to experience such a wonderful inclusive event."

Pre-Conference Workshops

The pre-conference workshops also took place on Monday 19 September in a number of locations.

The Measuring Walking: New smart tools and what can be done with good walking data

workshop with Daniel Sauter of the Urban Mobility Research Group in Switzerland has been running at the Walk21 conference for many years and is always popular. This workshop took place in the TU Dublin's School of Architecture, Building & Environment in Linen Hall, Dublin 1.

The discussion centered around evidence-based walking actions: showcasing walking research, data collection, project evaluations and staff training system that are increasing knowledge, skills and building capacity for delivering actions for people walking. The Decade to Change was also discussed; celebrating national ambition for walking - exploring how walking is being valued, invested in and monitored, especially in relation to addressing the climate emergency and delivering on the UN SDGs.

Figure 14: Prof. Marie Murphy from Ulster University presenting at the I-PARC Workshop

The workshop to **Introduce the I-PARC evaluation toolkit to measure the impact of physical activity interventions** was run by Dr. Enrique Garcia Sport Ireland, Prof. Niamh Murphy Waterford Institute of Technology, Prof. Marie Murphy Ulster University, Dr Joey Murphy University of Bristol, and Prof. Catherine Woods University of Limerick. This workshop took place at the Dogpatch Labs room in the CHQ Building.

The workshop on **Walking and the Law** was presented by Kate Robertson from the World Health Organisation and Carly Gilbert-Patrick from the United National Environmental Programme (UNEP). This workshop took place in the Liffey Room at the EPIC Museum in the CHQ Building.

The workshop on **Using Bluetooth Low Energy to study pedestrian activity in outdoor public spaces** by the TU Dublin tPOT research group changed its format from a practical interactive workshop to a discussion forum which has informed research projects and international collaborations since the event. This workshop took place in the Greenway Hub in TU Dublin's Grangegorman campus.

The **Exploring shortcuts as a tool and strategy to promote everyday walking** workshop was run by Dr Maja Karoline Rynning and Marianne Knapskog from the Institute of Transport Economics in Norway and Emmet O'Briain from TU Dublin. This workshop took place in the Annie Moore room at the EPIC Museum in the CHQ Building.

The workshop on **Active Travel Advocacy; Tales and Learning from the Front Lines** was delivered by Anne Cronin from the Limerick Cycling Campaign and Dr Madeleine Lyes from the Limerick Pedestrian Network. The workshop was a knowledge sharing exercise allowing for networking and support within active travel advocacy in Ireland; and secondly, the co-creation of an informal guide to advocacy in the Irish active travel context, derived from workshopped materials. This afternoon workshop took place in the Annie Moore room at the EPIC Museum in the CHQ Building.

Workshop feedback:

“The discussions were really interesting, the presentations also. It was a great way to start the conference.”

“It was my first conference and everything was a highlight for me. I was impressed by the speakers. I really liked the workshops too.”

Two invite-only workshops happened alongside the open registration workshops. **The UN Environment programme and World Health Organisation (WHO) regional office for Europe's Transport, Health and Environment Pan-European Partnership on Active Mobility (THE PEP)** held their first meetings as part of the Walk21 Ireland Conference. The partnership meeting was held before the other conference events so that participants could partake in and get inspired by the conference and the group reconvened on the Friday to discuss how the conference inspired them. The Assistant Secretary Department of Transport, Garret Doocey, welcomed the THE PEP Partnership on Active Mobility, and kickstarted the series of meetings which will provide space for reflection against the background of a national walking strategy and the pan-European Master Plan Walking. Their meetings took place in TU Dublin's Greenway Hub on the Grangegorman campus.

Figure 15: Garret Doocey Assistant Secretary Department of Transport welcoming the THE PEP Partnership on

The second invite only workshop was run by the VREF Research Foundation to coincide with their funding call on Walking as a Mode of Transport (WALKING). The convened expert group worked on research themes for the funding call and to network and develop the community of learning for walking as a mode of transport. This workshop took place in the Dogpatch Labs in the CHQ Building.

Opening Ceremony

Lord Mayor of Dublin Caroline Conroy officially opened the conference at a reception hosted by Dublin City Council in the EPIC Museum. The group was also welcomed by TU Dublin President Professor David FitzPatrick and MEP for Dublin in the European Parliament Ciarán Cuffe. The [Walk21 Europe Foundation](#) was also formally launched at the opening reception.

Figure 16: Lord Mayor of Dublin Caroline Conroy addressing delegates at the Welcome Reception

Figure 17: Prof. David FitzPatrick TU Dublin welcoming delegates at the Welcome Reception

Figure 18: Ciarán Cuffe MEP addressing delegates at the Welcome Reception

Figure 19: Walk21 Europe Foundation Trustees at the Opening Reception

Plenary 1 - Global Perspectives, National Commitment, Local Action: The Research and Political Momentum for Walking

Tuesday 20 September 2022 9:00-10.30am, Room EQ-010, East Quad, TU Dublin, Grangegorman campus.

The purpose of this session was to open the conference with a global view of the walking agenda in practice, policy and academia, followed by insights into the national investments and campaigns happening in Ireland to support walking.

Playback: [Plenary 1 Recording Link](#).

Ministerial and Officials Address:

- *TU Dublin Welcome* - Prof. David Fitzpatrick - President, TU Dublin, Ireland
- *Walk21 Welcome* - Bronwen Thornton - Walk21, United Kingdom
- *Welcome Address* - via video link from Minister Éamon Ryan, Minister for Transport, Climate and Communications.
- *A global view on the academic study of walking* - Dr Lake Sagaris - Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile

- *Austrian Federal Masterplan for Walking* - Robert Thaler - Environment Agency Austria
- *Ireland's Walking Story: Get Ireland Walking* - Dr Úna May - CEO, Sport Ireland
- *Ireland's Walking Story: investing in the infrastructure* - Joe Seymour - Head of Active Travel Investment, National Transport Authority
- *Youth Forum Call to Action* - Youth Forum representatives

Figure 20: Dr Lake Sagaris

Plenary 2 - Walking as the Foundation for Healthy Bodies, Minds and Streets

Tuesday 20 September 2022 14:00-15:30pm, Room EQ-010, East Quad, TU Dublin
Grangegorman campus.

This session challenged whether we are walking in nature or meeting people on urban streets, the environment around us is a key determinant of our decision to walk - or not - which influences our health and wellbeing. The session explored the role that the built environment has on our physical, social and psychological health with leading experts in this space.

Playback: [Plenary 2 Recording Link.](#)

Ministerial Address - Minister Maree Todd - Minister for Public Health, Women's Health and Sport, Scotland.

The Role of Place in Wellbeing - Prof. Esther Sternberg - University of Arizona, United States.

Panel: Building on the synergies between health and transport for better community outcomes.

Chaired by Dr Lorraine D'Arcy TU Dublin

Prof. Shane O'Mara - Trinity College Dublin, Ireland

Kate Robertson - World Health Organisation, Switzerland

Prof. Niall Moyna - Dublin City University, Ireland

Charlie Burke - Coillte, Ireland

José Besselink - City of Rotterdam, Netherlands

Figure 21: Prof. Esther Sternberg - University of Arizona

Plenary 3 - Ensuring Equity and Access for Everyone

Wednesday 21 September 2022 09:00-10:30am, Room EQ-010, East Quad, TU Dublin
Grangegorman campus.

Our streets and paths are places that we should all belong and where everyone feels safe, comfortable and welcome. We will hear about the walking experiences of African Americans, how academia can build understanding across divides, and be inspired by international advocates and the stories of people who decided to take action.

Playback: [Plenary 3 Recording Link](#).

Ministerial Address - Minister Jack Chambers - Minister of State with responsibility for Sport & the Gaeltacht, Ireland.

Equitable Cities - Charles Brown - Equitable Cities, United States.

Enhancing collaboration across academic disciplines and with society - Prof. Luca Bertolini - University of Amsterdam, Netherlands.

Figure 22: Charles Brown, Equitable Cities

Figure 23: Minister Jack Chambers addressing Plenary 3

Panel: Advocacy for all People Walking

Chaired by Bronwen Thornton Walk21

Dr Madeline Lyes - Irish Pedestrian Network, Ireland

Rona Gibb - Paths for All, Scotland

Stephen Edwards - Living Streets, United Kingdom

A personal journey: Interview with Neasa Hourigan, Green Party TD, Ireland and her daughter Edith Toomey.

Figure 24: Edith Toomey with her mother Neasa Hourigan, Green Party TD, Ireland

Plenary 4 - Building for Walking: Hard Yards or Easy Street?

Wednesday 21 September 2022 16:00-17:30pm, Room EQ-010, East Quad, TU Dublin
Grangegorman campus.

Walking for transport or recreation needs infrastructure and facilities like any other mode. Walking is easy, but building for it see harder and needs investment, political commitment and community support. This plenary session hosts speakers from these different perspectives and from cities around the World to explore how they are making the hard decisions to build for walking. Introductions given by Jennifer Boyer, Vice President for Sustainability TU Dublin.

Playback: [Plenary 4 Recording Link.](#)

Ministerial Address - Minister Éamon Ryan - Minister for Transport, Minister for the Environment, Climate and Communication, Ireland

European Perspective on Walking - Ciarán Cuffe - Member of European Parliament, Ireland

Delivering Waterford Greenway and other city projects - Michael Walsh - Chief Executive of Waterford City and County Council

Panel: Overcoming challenges to deliver walking facilities

Chaired by Ciarán Cuffe

Oddrun Helen Hagen - Institute of Transport Economics, Norwegian Centre for Transport

Anuela Ristini - Deputy Mayor of Tirana, Albania

Robert Burns - Director of Fingal County Council, Ireland

Emilie Herssens - Walk. Brussels, Belgium

Stewart Logan - Senior Executive Planner, Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage, Ireland

Figure 25: Minister Éamon Ryan addressing Plenary 4

World Café - How can we Make Walking Safer and More Secure to Help Deliver SDG Commitments by 2030?

Wednesday 21 September 2022 16:00-17:30pm, Room EQ-010, East Quad, TU Dublin Grangegorman campus.

Playback: World Café can be viewed [here](#).

A key aim of Walk21 Ireland was to encourage interdisciplinary interactions and to give Irish policymakers, practitioners, advocates and academics the opportunity to meet and learn from the international walking community. The intention of the world café at the conference was to bring delegates together to tease out interdisciplinary approaches to the grand challenges around walking; safety, security and sustainability. A review was undertaken of global documentation around safety, security, sustainability and gender and 159 actions were identified. Inspired by these actions, themes were set to inform the discussions, the outcomes of which will be brought forward to inform the international conversations around walking. It was intended that the world café event would be held in a large flat space in the National Sports Campus. Unfortunately, that space became unavailable to us shortly before the

conference because of a response to a national emergency. The world café was reformatted to work in a number of breakout room in the East Quad in TU Dublin following some scene-setting presentations.

Ministerial Address - Minister Frank Feighan - Minister of State for Public Health and the National Drugs Strategy

Presentations:

Pedestrian Safety: Angie Schmitt

Gender and Public Space: Heather Allen

Equity in the 'walk space': linking walkability with equity in informal settings: Prof. Adrian Davis

World café and feedback session chaired by Holgar Dalkman, Sustain 2030

Figure 26: Heather Allen

Figure 27: World Café feedback session Holgar Dalkman, Angie Schmitt, Prof. Adrian Davis and Heather Allen, The World Café tool is a format for hosting large group dialogue. Delegates sit at tables with flip chart paper and pens. After an introduction and scene setting the process begins with the first of three twenty-minute rounds of conversation at each table. At the end of the round, each group member moves to a new table. They may choose to leave one person as the “table host” for the next round, who welcomes the next group and updates them on what happened in the previous round. After the groups, individuals are invited to share insights with the large group. These results are reflected visually in the front of the room. The key outputs from the World Café exercise are listed in Appendix D under the headings of Safety, Equity and Gender. Within these there are 77 items which can be summarised as:

- It is important to differentiate between the perception of safety and actual safety when making policy and design decisions.
- The built environment should be designed with pedestrians in mind first, not last.
- National legislation is needed that prioritised pedestrians and controls driver behaviours.
- Enough data is not being collected and existing data is being ignored in conversations around road safety.
- People working together is key to social equity and it is essential to include a bottom up approach, include all people and the outputs of these discussions be engrained in planning and design decisions.
- Women of all ages must be included in planning and design of spaces and delivery of infrastructure.
- We need societal change around considerations for gender in transport and greater inclusivity.

Figure 28: World Café discussions

Figure 29: Jason King, Get Ireland Walking World Café group feedback

The Thursday event was poorly attended by Irish delegates which was disappointing as a key aim for this session was to give them the opportunity to engage in cross-disciplinary problem-based discussion with the international delegates. In hindsight, perhaps this was not stressed enough in the promotion of the event. Also, the change of venue and restructuring of the session to adapt to the new venue had mixed blessings. The logistics that were required to bring delegates to the Sports Campus may have resulted in even less delegates attending. There was a saving made in staging costs when the Thursday was moved to Grangegorman where the staging was already set up.

In their 2022 end of year meeting, the Get Ireland Walking Steering Committee expressed an interest in re-convening the Irish delegates from across disciplines a year post the Walk21 Ireland conference to revisit the learnings and how these have informed their work. It is intended to use the outcomes from the World Café, the Youth Forum and other Walk21 Ireland outputs as the basis to structure the discussion topics for that event.

Figure 30: Holgar Dalkman, Sustain 2030, opening the World Café

Plenary 5 - Closing Plenary: Walking Purposefully Through the Decade for Change

Thursday 22 September 2022, 15:15-16:00pm, Room EQ-010, East Quad, TU Dublin
Grangegorman campus.

Closing Plenary:

Global Designing Cities Initiative: Skye Duncan,

Conclusion: Jim Walker, Walk21

Handover: Prof. David FitzPatrick

Playback: [Plenary 5 Recording Link.](#)

Skye Duncan delivered an impactful closing plenary with a call to action from a global agenda to local action where we inspire leaders, we inform practitioners and empower communities which strongly reflected the core aim of the Walk21 Ireland conference.

Figure 31: Skye Duncan, The Global Designing Cities Initiative

Jim Walker delivered his concluding remarks on the conference which will be reflected upon in the post conference review section of this report. The next host of the Walk21 Conference were announced as the City of Kigali and the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP). Carley Gilbert-Patrick of UNEP delivered the acceptance and invitation to Kigali via a video link. Professor David FitzPatrick of TU Dublin presented the next hosts with a special centenary commemoration copy of the famous Irish book by Ulysses by James Joyce. The book is about a day in the life of a character Leopold Bloom and a day he spends walking the streets of Dublin.

Figure 32: Prof. FitzPatrick, TU Dublin, presenting Ulysses to Jim Walker as a handover gift to the Walk21 Kigali

Walkshops

Walkshops are a unique opportunity for applied learning and knowledge sharing. A diversity of topics were covered in these sessions that were well received by delegates.

Feedback

Like the workshops, walkshops were well received with the vast majority of people satisfied or

Figure 33: Outdoor Navigation for People who are Blind or Visually Impaired walkshop led by the NCBI.

very satisfied. Only three respondents were dissatisfied with their walkshop experience. The three most popular walkshops were:

- Nightwalking in Temple Bar with Leni Schwendinger and The Temple Bar Company
- Impact Storytelling & Youth Engagement with Pedestrian Dignity with Jonathon Stalls, Walking Artist
- Outdoor navigation for people who are blind or vision impaired by Chantelle Smith of the National Council for the Blind Ireland

“Walkshops - It puts theory into practice. Very much appreciated.”

“The walkshop...was an amazing way to learn, meet and connect with people from other places.”

“I attended "Impact storytelling and youth engagement " and "Walking the LIFELINE", both were excellent experiences.”

“The walkshop led by Chantelle Smith was very useful to me as a designer and broadened my understanding of the challenges faced by people with a visual impairment.”

WALK21 IRELAND

Join our workshops!
Mon 20 - Wed 22 Sept, Dublin

Monday 19 September, Dublin

- Night Walking in Temple Bar: safety & enjoyment for all - Leni Schwendinger (International Nighttime Design Initiative, USA)

Tuesday 20 September, Dublin

- Healthy TU Dublin Heritage Trails & Walkshops - Teresa Hurley (TU Dublin)
- Explore Urban Textures - Raphael Mak (Metrunner, Sweden)
- Impact Storytelling & Youth Engagement - Jonathon Stalls (Pedestrian Dignity, USA)
- Walking into Walkability Data: Exploring ways we assess and understand walking environments - Emmet Ó Briain (TU Dublin)
- Orienteering Walkshop: How do we navigate in cities? - Raphael Mak (Metrunner, Sweden)

Wednesday 22 September

- Every Step of the Way - Jim Walker (Walk21)
- Outdoor Navigation for People who are Blind or Vision Impaired: Experiences, Challenges and Future Directions - Chantelle Smith (NCBI, Ireland)
- Pedestrian Experience Assessment around public transport through the eye different users - Yaz Viramontes (CAMINA Centre for Pedestrian Mobility Studies, Mexico)
- Talking Nature in the City - Ken Boyle, TU Dublin
- Walking the LIFELINE, a living laboratory connecting nature, people and place - Kaethe Burt - O'Dea (desireland, Ireland)
- Bridgefoot Park & the Liberties - Stephen Coyne (Dublin City Council)

19 - 23 September 2022
THE DECADE TO CHANGE

 walk21ireland.com | [#walk21ireland](https://twitter.com/walk21ireland)

Figure 34: Walk21 Ireland Walkshop schedule

Parallel, Roundtable and Poster Sessions

In line with the aim and motivation for the conference the programme committee were particularly mindful of creating sessions that brought diverse disciplines together around key themes. The result of this is outlined in the full programme outlined in Appendix C where descriptions of the 29 sessions and 130+ contributions and weblinks to recordings can be found. Some of the topical discussion parallel sessions were hybrid to allow presenters contribute remotely and engage in discussion in the room. Questions could also be asked by remote delegates. A special thank you must be given to the session moderators and room assistants who volunteered to contribute in these roles. Posters were both displayed at the conference and available on the HopIn conference platform.

Figure 35: Roundtable session by the Global Street Design Initiative

Social Events

A key part of a successful conference are the opportunities to socialise, network and to experience the host's city and all that it has to offer. A number of social events were planned by the delivery team and there were also a number of impromptu informal social events organised by the conference volunteers. The recently closed to traffic Capel Street became a key location for informal socializing with groups of delegates to be found frequenting the cafes and bars along the street most evenings post conference events.

On Monday evening the Welcome Reception in the EPIC Museum was well attended by conference delegates. On Tuesday and Wednesday morning TU Dublin Walking PhD Researcher, and avid runner, Emmet O'Briain organised group runs in the Phoenix Park close to Grangegorman. There were also walkers with the group. Tuesday evening there was a conference dinner in the Round Room in the Mansion House, the Lord Mayors Residence, where delegates were entertained by The TU Dublin Harp Ensemble and an Irish traditional music group. On Wednesday evening delegates were invited to join us at McGowans Pub in Phibsborough, close to the TU Dublin Grangegorman campus, for a céilí and some food and drinks. An authentic Irish pub experience.

Figure 36: Conference Welcome Reception at EPIC Museum

Figure 37: Conference Dinner at the Round Room at the Mansion House

National Events

Throughout the conference planning the importance that Walk21 Ireland be a national conference in so far that it was possible was integral in the event design. The conference week led into National Walking Day on Sunday 25 of September and delegates were informed from the very start of the conference communications that there would be a number of walking events held around the country and to factor this into their conference travel plans if they wished.

On Friday 23 of September, which also happened to be Culture Night in Ireland, formal Walk21 Ireland associated events happened in Limerick, Cork and Dublin.

In Cork, Cork Sports Partnership, Get Ireland Walking and Cork County Council came together to host a walk and talk to showcase projects in the city, a networking lunch and presentations from local and international contributors. The events ran from 10:30am for roughly five hours.

In Limerick, the Limerick Pedestrian Network and Limerick Cycle Bus, supported by Limerick City and County Council Active Travel unit, presented a celebration of the Three Bridges Walk at the heart of Limerick City.

Figure 38: Attendees at Get Cork Walking's Walk21 Ireland satellite event

Figure 39: Map of Limerick Pedestrian Network's Walk21 Ireland walking satellite event as part of Culture Night

Figure 40: Grangegorman Histories Walking Tour of Grangegorman campus as part of Culture Night

Among the Culture Night Events in Dublin the Grangegorman Development Agency ran a historical tour of the campus and Bohemians Football Club had an event to showcase their App guided walking tour of Dublin 7, [The Bohemian Way](#). These events were highlighted to conference delegates.

In Dublin, TU Dublin's Dr Ken Boyle led a 2-hour long walk along the cliffs on Howth Head in Dublin. During the walk delegates met with representatives of the local authority, community groups and conservation ecologists in a discussion on the challenges of managing this resource.

Figure 41: Howth Head Walk with Dr Ken Boyle

Post Conference Review and Reflections

Communications

Communications and public relations support during the conference was provided by a number of team working together. The TU Dublin Sustainability Media and Senior Events Coordinator Rebecca Flanagan joined TU Dublin just before the conference and worked with the TU Dublin Communications & Marketing team to promote the conference and the University through various media channels. TU Dublin also collaborated with the funding agencies and other organisational partners to amplify the message and visibility of the event. Ralf Tinga from Walk21 International coordinated their communications channels which had a wider international audience.

‘We need to think more about how walking can help us overcome violence’

A conference in Dublin looked at how to make our cities safer and less car-dependent

Pedestrian advocate Peatonito from Mexico stops traffic on Custom House Quay with pupils from Dublin 7 Educate Together, on the first day of the global walking conference, Walk 21 Ireland. Photograph: Glasseye

Sylvia Thompson
Sat Sep 24 2022 - 05:00

Figure 42: National press media coverage of Walk21 Ireland featured on the Irish Times, [article by Sylvia Thompson](#)

Alice PR, an external public relations agency, was also contracted to look after the public relations for the conference from July to September 2022. Their main objectives included pitching speakers to environmental/infrastructure and planning/health and wellbeing media, producing social media graphics to promote the conference and attend Walk21 Ireland as required to manage photocall and media delegates. Alice PR reported that their campaign media reached over 3.5 million interactions from 12 online media pieces, 2 broadcasts and 22 print media articles. The coverage highlights included a feature piece in the Irish Times Weekend by Sylvia Thompson, and a piece in the Dublin Inquirer on whether Dubliners could do their ‘big shop’ on foot. Over the four days of the conference (when Alice PR were posting and managing Twitter content) the Walk21 Twitter generated 11,490 impressions and 2.7% engagement rate.

Website

The Walk21 Ireland website went live on Friday, 20 May 2022. Between then and October 2022 had 42k total views, 83k unique events with 4.1k new users and 1.5k returning visitors. Most visitors found the website directly, with social media accountable for the second highest percentage of visitors. The top three pages visited were the Home, Programme, and Registration pages respectively. Usage peaked in the lead up to and during the conference with a peak of 553 daily users on Tuesday, 20 September. The majority of visitors were based in the Republic of Ireland (2.5k or 61% of visitors).

Users ▾ by Country

Figure 43: Walk21 Ireland Website Users by Country

Communications conclusion

In general, the conference delivery team were happy with the media coverage and social media interactions achieved. A key learning for the team was the importance of having pre-prepared content for the journalists. Some of our advisory team's agencies/workplaces were excellent in sharing and amplifying content. Those with dedicated communications teams were particularly helpful.

Figure 44: Media interview, with Walk21 Rotterdam Lead 2019, José Besselink, City of Rotterdam

Youth participation was a key aim of the conference and the conference team were delighted to have RTÉ Ecolution podcast, an environmentally focused podcast for kids, come to the conference and interview participants at the youth forum. Listen to the feature on [Episode: 58 – Stepping out for Walk21 Ireland](#).

Social media

Twitter was the main social platform used and a new @Walk21Ireland account was created. As the main social media platform used by Walk21, the organisation had 4,788 followers on Twitter before the conference. During the conference, both Twitter accounts were managed and updated consistently. The hashtag #walk21ireland had been in use by the team in advance of the conference and it's use was actively encouraged throughout the conference, for example by adding it with the account handle to the conference lanyard and in all tweets. Engagement with the Walk21 and Walk21 Twitter accounts is detailed below.

Platform	Walk21	TU Dublin	Dept Health	Dept Sport	Dept Transport	Combined Audience
Twitter	4788	23,100	135,700	15,500	2763	181,851
LinkedIn	602	134,362	16,463	4187	--	155,614
Facebook	2858	44,071	4203	10,911	--	62,043
Instagram	298	15,300	4316	11,100	--	31,014

	Tweets	Tweet impressions	Profile visits	Mentions
Walk21	57	48,696	22,221	474
Walk21 Ireland	247	252,056	34,282	800

Table 1: Key stakeholder and Walk21 social media engagement across main platforms

Funding and Spend

The conference planning was carried out in a period of great international uncertainty and national responsiveness; the Steering Committee's decision making throughout the process was mindful of the challenges that were going to impact the delivery of the conference. As outlined earlier in this report equity, accessibility, ethical considerations and sustainability were at the core of all decisions while also delivering a high-quality event. The Steering Committee and delivery team were also mindful that there would be a cohort of people and groups that would learn about the event and its relevance after the event. This was a particularly relevant consideration in the context of walking as a topic since its applicability to many professions is not always obviously apparent. Therefore, the production of high-quality recordings and conference media to be made freely available after the event was important. This openly accessible media resource contains over 300 hours of recorded material.

Ticket prices were decided upon and agreed by the Steering Committee to be reflective of the high-quality event being produced but also not be prohibitively high. The cost of a full ticket was half the price of comparative transport conferences hosted in Ireland in recent years. Early bird rates, group discounts, speaker rates and volunteer tickets were all made available to delegates. These concessions and the delivery of the high-quality event were all possible because of the generous funding contributions from the government departments and sponsors. The Steering Committee agreed that surplus funds from ticket sales can be held by TU Dublin and reinvested in walking related research and actions. As of August 2023, an Action Researcher has been employed on a part-time 3-year contract with TU Dublin to work on these Walk21 Ireland legacy projects including a follow up Irish event with Get Ireland Walking, action research projects and continued societal engagement with the stakeholder network that has grown from the conference.

Table 11 outlines the income and expenditure for the Walk21 Ireland project. Please note that Contributions in Kind from TU Dublin have not been included in this table but come to an estimated €75,000 staffing and administration support on top of the salaries included in the project costs and €15,000 in venue hire.

Income:	
Government of Ireland Funding – Department of Health/ Healthy Ireland	€250,000
Government of Ireland Funding – Department of Transport	€250,000
Government of Ireland Funding – Sport Ireland on behalf of Department of Tourism, Culture, Arts, Gaeltacht, Sport & Media	€250,000
Specific Item Sponsorship – Dublin City Council Youth Forum & Opening Ceremony	€20,000
Specific Item Sponsorship – Fingal County Council World Café	€20,000
Speaker Sponsorship Contributions DBFL Consulting Engineers & Galway City Council	€3,500
Specific Item Sponsorship – VREF – International Researcher Bursaries & Speaker Sponsorship Contribution	€18,500
Ticket Sales (minus platform fees)	€81,608
Total Income:	€893,608
Expenditure:	
Venue Hire, Staging, AV systems, Catering and Wayfinding	€242,402
Conference Dinner and Social Events	€47,084
Online Conferencing Systems	€20,940
Invited Speakers travel and accommodation costs	€42,668
VREF Bursary awardees costs	€14,575
Student Transport to Youth Forum	€394
Branding, Photography and Communications	€89,823
Walk21 Licence Fee and expenses	€70,000
Event Management & Support	€193,280
TU Dublin Staffing Costs	€96,205
Total Expenditure:	€817,371
Surplus	€76,236

Table 2: Conference Income and Expenditure

Conference Conclusions

In the closing plenary, Walk 21 International's Jim Walker reflected on how the focus of this year's event was on delivering action. That COVID-19 responses had proven change could be delivered quickly, with minimum budgets and was valued by communities. Nearly 100 actions were proposed by the Youth Forum to improve walking for people in Ireland. A further 30 were added over the following days to ensure the strategic goals for improving equity, road safety and sustainability could also be delivered through investments in walking anywhere.

He spoke about how Ireland taught the international walking community that we need good evidence, policy, and budgets to deliver community walkability but that these are most likely as an outcome of joined up thinking across government departments. He commended how politicians at a national level, from three different parties, as well as three different Ministries, demonstrated the demand for better walkability is fundamental to life quality and a common goal for better transport, climate, sport and health outcomes. He noted that universities proved valuable too, for upskilling teams, accumulating a library of resources, and making sure government policy is evidence based and able to be evaluated independently for impact.

Inputs from countries, like Scotland, reminded us that it can be helpful to fund advocates at a community level to ensure government funding for walking gets spent where it's needed locally.

He suggested that the Irish Pedestrian Network has the potential for ensuring the detail that is being demanded gets delivered and should inspire other advocate groups to ask. Public transport catchments that are walkable for women; pedestrian crossings that are safe for people with disabilities; and schools that have footpaths connecting to residential areas, are all logical community demands that were highlighted in Ireland and priorities that any country should deliver. The tenfold increase in the budget for Active Travel (from €30 million to €360 million) at the Department for Transport is a good indication of the scale of investment

required for walking from national governments, to deliver the foundation of a sustainable transport paradigm and is an inspiration to other departments and countries.

The 'Decade to Change' conference theme stressed the urgency to deliver at a pace and in parallel to a change in mindset from designing urban spaces, systems, and networks around cars to people. Through conference contributions we were reminded that the shift has been in a generation, to an Ireland where most children are driven to school, students are driving to college; and older people drive to the park to go for a walk. Many, if not most of these trips could easily be walked. What changed and what now needs to change?

Figure 45: Jim Walker, Walk21, delivering Conference conclusion

To make walking safer, more secure and sustainable and help deliver the Sustainable Development Goal commitments by 2030 the following actions are of specific note from the 130+ listed during the conference:

1. Broaden the view of transport beyond male dominated commuting patterns.
2. Include women of all ages in the planning and design of public space and delivery of infrastructure and public amenities.
3. Empower girls and women to be equal users of public space.
4. Provide more education for boys around women's safety fears and harassment.
5. Invest in walkability to tackle the growth of social violence so that women, children and older people feel welcome in streets and public space.
6. Young people ask especially for: better, wider and more footpaths, more shortcuts, better lighting, more enforcement of traffic speeds, parking on footpaths and design for safety, and more places to go and safe places to hang out.
7. Give priority to pedestrians first as a solution to road danger. Focus on accessibility and permeability, comfort, capacity and maintenance.
8. Manage traffic with legislation, taxation and enforcement, in parallel to making the pedestrian experience better.
9. Invite citizens to map their experiences to understand existing barriers and any differences by income, gender and in rural townlands especially.
10. Legislate rights of way to secure long term community access.

Going forward, to build upon discussion at Walk21 Ireland the 2023 conference in Kigali, Rwanda should focus on women and walking; the finance mechanism for funding investment in walking; and how walkability can support the achievement of the Paris climate goals. It was noted that the success of the model where the university hosted the conference in partnership with government that the 2023 hosts have reached out to the University of Rwanda.

Figure 46: Prof. FitzPatrick, TU Dublin, presenting Ulysses to Jim Walker as a handover gift to the Walk21 Kigali Team

Reflections from TU Dublin

Hosting Walk21 Ireland was a great pleasure for TU Dublin. Sustainability is core to what the University wishes to deliver and Walk21 Ireland was our first major strategic sustainability event which we were able to deliver internally as a national conference to have impact across Ireland and the world. The TU Dublin President has advised the conference Steering Committee of the positive comments he has received from the respective Ministers and those involved and the event would not have been achieved without Jim Walker and Bronwen Thornton from Walk21 and their colleagues, with such significant support from the three Departments which allowed the event to be a success for the University and nationally. He noted that he is very proud of what was achieved in putting Ireland on the map and what we are doing in the University. He expressed a huge thanks to those involved. Jennifer Boyer, Vice President for Sustainability has re-iterated these comments acknowledging the whole government approach and welcomes this ongoing approach to action sustainability nationally.

Organising an event of this magnitude was not without its challenges and a lot of lessons were learnt in the process. The new contacts, networks and the knowledge gained will be utilised to build upon the open dialogue around interdisciplinary action and innovation, the diversity in participatory events and the societal engagement that was highlighted in the event. TU Dublin now have a live action research model as a result of this conference re: climate, education, training and how to spend money on walking. The Walk21 Ireland Advisory Committee have expressed an interest in continuing as a group and there is an aspiration towards an annual Irish event, perhaps travelling around the country in different cities or areas which would be a wonderful legacy.

Conference Chair, Dr Lorraine D'Arcy has continued to receive very positive feedback from the conference and its ongoing impacts. From an educational perspective, students who attended the conference are already talking about their dissertations on this subject and some have reached out to speakers at the conference. The Youth Forum, which took place on the first day of the conference, received a lot of positive feedback. Dr D'Arcy thanks all those that bought into the concept of this interdisciplinary event, especially the Steering Committee who brought the funding to the table. A very special thank you to everyone that contributed to the event being such a wonderful success.

Figure 47: Walk21 Ireland Conference Lead, Dr Lorraine D'Arcy, TU Dublin

Legacy Projects Update

In September 2023, TU Dublin's Sustainability Office were successful awardees of Science Foundation Ireland (SFI) Sustainable Communities Challenge Funding for a project which focuses on Campus' Role as Actors in Walking and Liveability (CRAWL)⁶. Building upon the Walk21 Ireland conference, the project will use TU Dublin's three campus locations to engage with the existing network of Irish stakeholders on walkability and liveability, the three local authorities, the university community and surrounding communities to co-create a programme of action to improve the walkability of the campuses and their surrounds.

The core rationale for the project is that since the 1960's development patterns changed to a more suburban car-based approach for street and neighbourhood design. As we moved to this more suburban design, our university campuses followed suit and now we have challenges which include the social health of students and transport poverty (financial costs and time costs) due to long commute times and limited public transport options for commuting to campuses. Finding opportunities to improve campuses can have opportunities for transferability of good practice to other campus settings improving access to employment and healthcare. A citizen science air quality study will run across all locations alongside the co-creation of actions for each campus location.

A grant of €5,000 has been awarded to the Walk21 Kigali conference organisers from the Walk21 Ireland surplus funds to be used for travel scholarships for students from African nations to attend the conference in Kigali. TU Dublin PhD candidate, Ajeni Ari, has also received travel funding to attend the event in Kigali, Rwanda.

Plans are underway for TU Dublin and Get Ireland Walking to host a World Café on Walking in early 2024 to bring together Irish stakeholders to reflect on how Walk21 Ireland impacted and informed their work. Opportunities for more transdisciplinary collaborations will be explored.

Rialtas na hÉireann
Government of Ireland

⁶<https://www.sfi.ie/research-news/news/minister-final-NCF-teams/>

Appendix A – The Business Case for Walk21 Ireland

Business case for request for funding support for the Walk21 International Conference on Walking and Liveability, Ireland 2022 hosted by TU Dublin

TU Dublin will be hosting the 2022 Walk21 Conference on the week of the 19 - 23 September 2022. This aligns with European Mobility Week, National Walking Week and leads into the National Walking Day (Sunday, 25 September 2022) and European Week of Sport.

The conference presents an opportunity to engage with international experts and practitioners to empower local authorities, agencies and community groups, whether they are from Rural, Suburban or Urban settings, to make places more walkable and liveable.

Delegates are expected to attend from every continent and is likely to reach an audience of 5,000+ people. The Walk21 Seoul (online only) event in 2021 engaged 5,500 people and recent in-person events have been attended by 700 – 1,000 participants. Walk21 traditionally has been hosted in Europe every other year – due to strong demand from researchers, advocates and practitioners keen to participate and share their experiences. However, Rotterdam was the last host in 2019, and there are many national and city developments in waiting to report on. (European Horizon 2020 research projects; regional and national policy developments; COVID responses to walking and new research on financing walking for example). Emerging practitioners in Africa, Asia and Latin America (where Walk21 has been active growing support in the last 5 years especially) will be reached by an Ireland hybrid event – many of who are especially excited by Ireland’s visible national leadership for walking – in terms of political commitment to policy, funding and delivery.

TU Dublin honoured to take on the role of host institution for the event as the conference topic is closely aligned to TU Dublin’s strategic vision built on the three pillars of People, Planet and Partnership.

The key uniqueness of the Irish approach for Walk21 2022 is the interdisciplinary approach with a National focus. This was a key aim from the start of discussions around the Irish conference and key relevant Government departments and agencies were together to develop a vision for the event. Walking, Walkability and Liveability are topics of relevance to many disciplines and greater collaboration in this space will lead to better value for investment and greater collaborative working.

In light of continuing Covid-19 restrictions and uncertainty around social distancing restrictions as the global vaccination programme rolls out, coupled with the race against variants, it was decided that the most prudent approach for the 2022 conference would be a hybrid conference broadcast on a high-quality web interface with in person audiences. In the Get Ireland Walking Stakeholder event hosted by TU Dublin in February 2020 a preference was noted for the conference to be an ‘Ireland’ conference and not just a City hosted one. The proposed hybrid nature of the conference now gives greater flexibility and potential for geographical distribution of events.

This hybrid approach is also a more environmentally friendly and equitable approach to information sharing in a global conference format.

TU Dublin are requesting €741,500 from Government to fund the delivery of the hybrid conference which will be hosted from venues in Dublin City and other locations around Ireland. An outline of the budget request is attached.

The potential impact from this event is far reaching from National and International Policy and collaboration right down to grassroots implementation and community engagement and ownership. Workshops and ‘walkshops’ locally hosted around Ireland with contributions from international experts with contexts relatable to many practitioners home and abroad will be a key feature of the event. The increasing publicly funded local workforce in this space will benefit greatly.

Walking is an activity that is available to all. Good design and provision for walking (walkability) serves those that wish to walk, run, push or roll.

An increasing emphasis is being placed on the importance of research to understand the determinants of walking behaviour; what prevents people walking in their neighbourhood, the role of walking and nature for good physical and mental health, the role of neighbourhood in social connectedness and participation in civic society. The conference covers academic research but a greater emphasis is placed on showcasing real projects and programmes rolled out by local authorities and organisations all over the globe.

Good walkability and liveability are central to the Irish Programme for Government as they:

- contribute to a better quality of life for all • are key considerations for neighbourhood and regional planning within the National Development Plan (NDP).
- are important for domestic and international tourism.
- can reduce transport related carbon emissions and improve air quality.
- walking is an equitable form of transport available to all at no cost.
- allow greater appreciation of our natural and built heritage and biodiversity.
- contribute to greater wellbeing and has a role in preventative medicine.
- contribute to urban regeneration and makes urban centres more attractive for living and commerce.
- provide opportunities for rural development and community participation projects.
- are social provision, especially offering opportunities for community interactions and activity for those marginalised in society • lead to safer communities with greater social connectiveness.
- afford greater physical access to education and more attentive students from active commuting.
- are global topics of relevance for all climates, cultures and communities where we can learn from each other.
- are topics of relevance for a number of state departments, agencies and sections within our local authorities creating greater opportunities for collaborative interdisciplinary projects.

The event is relevant to the implementation of the following National Policies and Strategies (amongst others):

- Climate Action Plan
- National Planning Framework
- Our Rural Future
- Healthy Ireland Framework
- Sustainability Mobility Policy (upcoming)
- National Sports Policy 2018 - 2027
- Rural Regeneration Development Fund
- The Greenways Strategy
- Building Momentum - Local Authority Action Plan
- Cultural Capital Programme
- People, Place and Policy - Growing Tourism to 2025
- Community Enhancement Programme
- National Economic Recovery Plan
- Sharing the Vision: A Mental Health Policy for Everyone
- Get Ireland Walking Strategy & Action Plan 2017-2020
- National Physical Activity Plan
- Obesity Policy and Action Plan
- Urban Regeneration and Development Fund (URDF)
- National Spatial Strategy
- National Development Plan 2018-2027
- Project Ireland 2040

Appendix B – Committees and Partners

Walk21 Steering Committee Members:

TU Dublin

Jennifer Boyer - Vice President for Sustainability (Chair)

Dr Lorraine D’Arcy - Sustainability Action Research & Innovation Lead, Conference Lead

Walk21 Ireland 2022

Walk21

Bronwen Thornton- CEO

Jim Walker - Founder

Department of Health

Dr Fiona Mansergh - Health and Wellbeing Programme

Paul Brosnan - Health and Wellbeing Programme

Department of Transport

Derek O’Neill - National Roads, Greenways, and Active Travel Division (RIP)

Deirdre Donohoe - National Roads, Greenways, and Active Travel Division (November 2021 to September 2022)

Sarah Taylor - National Roads, Greenways, and Active Travel Division (October 2021 and September 2022 to October 2022)

Department of Tourism, Culture, Arts, Gaeltacht, Sport and Media

James Lavelle - Sports Policy and National Campus Division

Ian Smith - Sports Policy and National Campus Division

Gabriel O’Gorman - Sports Policy and National Campus Division (October 2021 to June 2022)

Sport Ireland

Louise Burke - Director, Participation (April 2022 to October 2022)

Dates of meetings held:

1. 14 October 2021
2. 03 November 2021 and addendum of 23 November 2021
3. 01 February 2022
4. 01 March 2022
5. 05 April 2022
6. 28 April 2022
7. 07 June 2022
8. 05 July 2022
9. 02 August 2022
10. 06 September 2022
11. 25 October 2022

Walk21 Advisory Committee

Michael Ahearn – National Transport Authority

Dr Jackie Bourke – Urban Geographer

Rachel Cahill – Transport Infrastructure Ireland

Christina Duff – Irish Heart Foundation

Leon Fox – Department of Rural and Community Affairs

Dr Michelle Hardie Murphy – Health Services Executive

Alison Harvey – Heritage Council

Christine Hegarty – Road Safety Authority

Kathleen Jacobi – Transport Infrastructure Ireland

Jason King – Get Ireland Walking

Prof. Kevin Leyden – NUI Galway

Madeleine Lyes – Irish Pedestrian Network

Antonia Martin – Dublin City Council

Ciara Munnely – Sport Ireland

Sarah O’Brien – Health Services Executive

Ruth C O’Reilly – National Disability Authority

Dr Lorraine D’Arcy (Chair) – TU Dublin

Walk21 Programme Committee

Dr Úna Beagon – TU Dublin

Dr Lorraine D’Arcy – TU Dublin

Dr David Gaul – TU Dublin

Jason King – Get Ireland Walking

David O’Connor – TU Dublin

Bronwen Thornton – Walk21

Jim Walker – Walk21

Walk21 International Review Committee

Prof. Aoife Ahern – University College Dublin

Paschalín Basil – University of Nairobi

Dr Damon Berry – TU Dublin

Dr William Bird – Intelligent Health

Sarah Bowman – Trinity College Dublin

Dr Ken Boyle – TU Dublin

Dr Tamara Bozovic – Auckland University of Technology

Robert Burns – Fingal County Council

Dr Marica Cassarino – University College Cork

Benny Cullen – Sport Ireland

Robyn Davies – Transport & Main Roads, Queensland

Dr Sabrina Dekker – Dublin City Council

Ailish Drake – Irish Pedestrian Network

Prof. Stefan Fina – RWTH Aachen University

Shreya Gadepalli – Urban Works Initiative

Carly Gilbert-Park – United Nations

Dr Michelle Hardie Murphy – Health Services Executive

Mary Harkin – Age and Opportunity

Dr Helge Hillnuter – Norwegian University of Science and Technology

Dr Mike Hynes – National University of Ireland, Galway

Dr Paul Kelly – Edinburgh University

Patrick Kinyanjui – Global Alliance of NGOs for Road Safety

Kate Kraft – Placemakers Guild

Prof. Kevin Leyden – National University of Ireland, Galway

Dr David Lindelow – Sweco

Natalia Llera – Partnership for Healthy Cities

Michael Mac Aree – National Transport Authority

Dr Tadhg MacIntyre – Maynooth University

Dr Suzanne Meade – Transport Infrastructure Ireland

Dr Alan Mee – University College Dublin

Dr Janis Morrissey – Irish Heart Foundation

Hannah Oblund – World Resources Institute

Dr Kate Pangbourne – Leeds University

Daria Raspopina – Centre for Urban Projects Shtab

Maja José Rojo – Empresa Municipal de Transportes de Madrid

Leticia Sabino – SampaPé

Dr Stefan Steiniger – CEDEUS Chile

Karen van der Spek – Municipality of Rotterdam

Prof. Catherine Woods – University of Limerick

Walk21 Ireland Delivery Team

Jennifer Boyer – TU Dublin

Anne Campion – TU Dublin

Clare Connell

Dr Lorraine D’Arcy – TU Dublin (Conference Chair)

Rebecca Flanagan – TU Dublin

Ailish Lally – Walk21 (Conference Coordinator)

Éadaoin Ryan – TU Dublin

Bronwen Thornton – Walk21

Ralf Tinga – Walk21

Jim Walker – Walk21

Appendix C – Parallel Sessions, Walkshops, Roundtables and Posters

Parallel Sessions

Tuesday 20 September 2022

Session 1/1: National and Regional Policymaking

11am to 12:30pm, Room EQ002, East Quad, TU Dublin Grangegorman campus

Playback: [Session Recording Link](#)

Description: How can national strategies support local walking? This session will explore the methods and tools for their development and share insights from implementation and increasing the profile of walking at all levels of government.

Characteristics of walking strategies - their usefulness and effect

Marianne Knapskog - Institute of Transport Economics, Norway

Austrian Federal Masterplan for Walking

Robert Thaler - Federal Ministry for Climate Action, Environment, Energy, Mobility, Innovation and Technology, Austria

National Walking Strategies

Paulo Cambra - U-Shift - Técnico Lisboa, University of Lisbon

Queensland steps up: Escalating the profile of walking at the state level

Robyn Davies - Department of Transport and Main Roads, Australia

The Irish Physical Activity Research Collaboration (I-PARC): all-island collaborative action for physical activity promotion and knowledge translation

Prof. Catherine Woods - University of Limerick, Ireland

Session 1/2: Creating Places for Children and Young People

11am to 12:30pm, Room EQ-116, East Quad, TU Dublin Grangegorman campus

Playback: [Session Recording Link](#)

Description: To create life-long walking habits it is essential that children feel safe and comfortable on our streets. In this session we learn from case studies and academic projects what we can do to create more child-friendly communities.

Walkability for Children in Bologna: An Urban Informatics Approach

Dr Andrea Gorrini - Fondazione Transform Transport ETS, Italy

Lessons learned from the Streets for Kids projects

Anna Siprikova - Global Designing Cities Initiative, United States

How to support walking - a child's perspective

Chiara Hanrahan - An Taisce, Ireland

Develop child-friendly urban planning principles for liveable and walkable neighborhoods – the use case of Westlich Kennedydamm and the “Move Düsseldorf” vision in Germany.

Ibrahim Alsalamh - Arup Deutschland GmbH

Encouraging Children to Walk to Learn

Roger Healey - Kingston Coalition for Active Transportation, Canada

Session 1/3 : Walk to the Line: joined-up thinking in public transport

11am to 12:30pm, Room EQ-112, East Quad, TU Dublin Grangegorman campus

Playback: [Session Recording Link](#)

Description: Good walking infrastructure is an essential part of any public transport network and can deliver both equity and health outcomes. In this session we explore the needs of a variety of user groups and how we can create more inclusive public transport systems that deliver both transport and public health benefits.

The needs and requirements of people with disabilities for 'walking' more often: Insights from the mobility survey of the TRIPS project

Dr Tally Hatzakis - Trilateral Research Ltd, Ireland

Inclusify: Women empowerment for inclusive mobility

Mariona Conill de Azpiazu - Àrea Metropolitana de Barcelona, Spain

Walk & Ride: Introducing the Public Transport Physical Activity Appraisal Toolkit

Martin Wedderburn - Wedderburn Transport Planning, United Kingdom

Evidence-based approach through a combination of new technologies and active youth participation to advocate for safer walking environment for children.

Quyen Bui - AIP Foundation, Vietnam

Session 1/4: Motivating People to Walk: what's the magic wand?

11am to 12:30pm, Room EQ-211, East Quad, TU Dublin Grangegorman campus

Playback: [Session Recording Link](#)

Description: Apps, social media or environmental changes - what encourages more people to walk more often? With examples from around the world, we will explore a diverse set of approaches from walking meetings to speed reduction.

Motivating Walking in Travel Apps

Dr Kate Pangbourne - Institute for Transport Studies, University of Leeds

First time experience of walking meetings: how to design onboarding solutions to promote this healthy work practice?

Mélodie Jacob - University of Luxembourg

A Saudi experience in using social media for including all people walking in Saudi Arabia, Gulf and Arab States

Dr Salih Alansari - Health Promotion Center, Saudi Arabia

Neighborhood shared streets under 30km/h: Pedestrian safety challenges beyond speed reduction

Dr Jihee Namgung - Architecture and Urban Research Institute, Republic of Korea

Session 1/5: Real-life road safety initiatives from around the World

11am to 12:30pm, Room EQ-009, East Quad, TU Dublin Grangegorman campus

Playback: [Session Recording Link](#)

Description: How do we design for pedestrian safety? In this session we will share global insights on overcoming challenges to delivering movement at a human pace with people-centered design for a range of different contexts.

Non-motorized visibility project

Galebowe Motlhajoe - Society of Road Safety Ambassadors, Botswana

Show me the way - Big Data Screening Methodology to identify road safety risk around schools and prioritize investments

Shanna Lucchesi - International Road Assessment Programme, Portugal

Loving 30 - A foundation for walking and everything else

Rod King - 20's Plenty for Us - Love 30, United Kingdom

The right of the city, the right of the students

Sonia Aguilar SONIA AGUILAR - World Resources Institute, México

How much do 30 km/h speed limits affect walkability?

Muireann O'Dea - Love 30, the Campaign for 30km/h Speed Limits, Ireland

Session 1/6: Pecha Kuchas

11am to 12:30pm, Room EQ-117, East Quad, TU Dublin Grangegorman campus

Playback: [Session Recording Link](#)

Description: Join a Pecha Kucha session to hear from a variety of projects in this dynamic, short-form presentation style.

"GRP" - an everyday route-planning tool for healthy mobility

Kathrin Chiu - Austrian Energy Agency

Exercise, Enliven, Encounter - Potential at the doorstep

Jenny Leuba - Pedestrian Mobility Switzerland

Safer Neighborhoods Emerging across the Global South

Abhimanyu Prakash - Global Designing Cities Initiative, United States

Connecting-Cabra - A community working to reclaim their streets for people

Dr Brian Gormley - Connecting-Cabra, Ireland

Slow roads set Antwerp in motion

Laura Nagels - Trage Wegen VZW, Belgium

Engaging Communities Through Walking Art

Sara Hayes - The Public Art Company, United Kingdom

The Shopping Trolley Project: A Small Investment with a Large Impact

Stuart Lindsay - Net Zero Vermont, United States

Location as a Service (LaaS): a neighborhood intelligence platform that facilitates the search for walkable neighborhoods

Dr Bernardita Calinao - WALKSPAN, United States

Session 2/1 : Evaluating Environments and their Walkability

4pm to 5:30pm, Room EQ-002, East Quad, TU Dublin Grangegorman campus

Playback: [Session Recording Link](#)

Description: What makes a walkable place and how do we measure walkability? In this session, we will discuss tools to measure the walkability of an area capturing a variety of user perspectives.

From STRIDE.App to Walkability.App - development of two apps to report walking experiences in the field

Dr Stefan Steiniger - Centro de Desarrollo Urbano Sustentable, Chile

From Local to National: A Universal Design Approach to Walkable Towns

Ruth O'Reilly - Centre for Excellence in Universal Design, National Disability Authority, Ireland

Virtual Reality for Improving Walkability

Prof. Stefan van der Spek - Delft University of Technology, Faculty of Architecture & Built Environment, Netherlands

Walkability Tool

Tomer Shachaf - GIS Specialist at PosadMaxwan, Netherlands

Walking Towards Inclusion for the Traveller Community in Finglas

Doireann Crosson - Pavee Point Traveller and Roma Centre, Ireland

Session 2/2: Walking to School: essential steps to support this journey

4pm to 5:30pm, Room EQ-116, East Quad, TU Dublin Grangegorman campus

Playback: [Session Recording Link](#)

Description: Every child should be able to get to school safely no matter where they are in the World. Examples of approaches to create safer routes from around the globe will be presented and discussed in this session.

Safe Access to Schools Initiative: A case study from Mumbai

Rohit Tak - World Resources Institute, India

New School Zone Paradigm in Korea based on Traffic Accident Analysis

Dr Sunghoon Oh - Architecture and Urban Research Institute, Republic of Korea

Streamlining the Safe Routes to School Programme in Rio de Janeiro

Danielle Hoppe - Institute for Transportation and Development Policy, Brazil

School streets, school zones - lessons from around the world

Richard Clarke - FIA Foundation, United Kingdom

Designing 'Playful' School Zones and the wider Safe Routes to School Programme

Finola O'Driscoll - National Transport Authority, Ireland

Session 2/3: Mobilising our Older Population

4pm to 5:30pm, Room EQ-112, East Quad, TU Dublin Grangegorman campus

Playback: [Session Recording Link](#)

Description: Environments that support us to walk, push, run or roll independently through our whole lives are key to a community's liveability. Ensuring that the elderly are well catered

for to enable this freedom is central to this session's presentations.

Elderly Mobility Plan, including seniors pedestrians in public spaces

Rodrigo Lurueña - Association Transports et Environnement, Switzerland

Enhancing Accessibility of Barrier-Free Routes for Elderly

Sarah Ang - Land Transport Authority, Singapore

Guangzhou's Ageing-friendly Transportation Strategy under the Goal of an All ages friendly City

Zexia Wang - Guangzhou Urban Planning & Design Survey Research Institute, China

Silver Ribbons: Research on user-friendly walking routes for seniors

Naomé Carmeliet - Voetgangersbeweging VZW, Belgium

Session 2/4: Walking to Win in Public Health and Planning:

4pm to 5:30pm, Room EQ-211, East Quad, TU Dublin Grangegorman campus

Playback: [Session Recording Link](#)

Description: Planning and public health are intrinsically linked but as practitioners from either the built environment or public health professions we aren't always sure how to communicate the successes of working together in meaningful ways. This session highlights ways that we can.

Wake-up Call from a Family Doctor in Rotterdam - How Active Mobility Can Serve Public Health

José Besselink - Urban Planner, Municipality, City of Rotterdam, Netherlands

The Healthy Cities Generator: Get to the heart of healthy Urban Planning

Ruth Gow - Bax & Company, Spain

Healthy Movement, Healthy Places: Measuring Wellbeing and Quality of Life Impacts in Transport Appraisal

Martin Wedderburn - Wedderburn Transport Planning, United Kingdom

Walking Interventions to Increase Active Commuting

Siobhan Hamilton - National Transport Authority, Ireland

Session 2/5: Wrestling with the Data: understanding what is needed and how to use it

4pm to 5:30pm, Room EQ-009, East Quad, TU Dublin Grangegorman campus

Playback: [Session Recording Link](#)

Description: In a data-rich world how do we know what the best data and collection methods are? How should we best use it? Surveys and tech solutions for walking and walkability data will be explored by this international group of experts.

Technologies to count pedestrians, typologies of flow profiles and extrapolation factors: examples from a comprehensive Swiss study

Daniel Sauter - Urban Mobility Research, Switzerland

Our right to a walkable city: assessing walkability and accessibility to the public space in Guayaquil

Prof. Isabel Escobar - Universidad de Especialidades Espíritu Santo, Ecuador

Automated extraction of pedestrian activity using Graph Databases

David Powell - tPOT Research Group, Ireland

Pedestrian typologies - a sociological look at urban walkways

Renate Albrecher - Ecole Polytechnic Fédéral de Lausanne, Switzerland

Session 2/6: Pechas Kuchas

4pm to 5:30pm, Room EQ-117, East Quad, TU Dublin Grangegorman campus

Playback: [Session Recording Link](#)

Description: Join a Pecha Kucha session to hear from a variety of projects in this dynamic, short-form presentation style.

Interim street transformation strategies in the self-built neighborhood of Jardim Monte Verde, Recife- Brazil.

Eduarda Aun - Global Designing Cities Initiative, United States

A Phenomenological Exploration of Landscape and Long-Distance Walking Practices on the Dingle Way

Dr Mary Dillon - Technological University Dublin, Ireland

Exploring Transport Doublespeak - the importance of storytelling in changing people's minds!

Mario Alves - International Federation of Pedestrians, Portugal

Safer School Zones

Galebowe Motlhajoe - Society of Road Safety Ambassadors, Botswana

Where the city meets the river - Riverside placemaking in Budapest

Berta Molnar - Centre for Budapest Transport, Hungary

Micro Mobility - Future mobility and inclusive design for Individuals who are Blind or Vision Impaired

Chantelle Smith - National Council for the Blind of Ireland, Ireland

Interim street transformation and speed reduction strategies in the downtown corridor Rua da Palma, Recife- Brazil

Antônio Oliveira - Prefeitura do Recife (Recife City Hall), Brazil

Pedestrians within and towards mobility hubs

Maxine Ketele - Infopunt Publieke Ruimte, Belgium

Wednesday 21 September 2022 - Parallel Sessions

Session 3/1: Walking in Women's Shoes

11am to 12:30pm, Room EQ-002, East Quad, TU Dublin Grangegorman campus

Playback: [Session Recording Link](#)

Description: The differences in our walking experiences are not just in the shoes we wear.

We need to build out bias in our approaches to public space and this session will share examples of places from around the world that have made better for women and girls.

Planning for gender-inclusive in urban areas: An application to the City of Naples (Italy)

Dr Carmen Guida - University of Naples Federico II, Italy

Walkability with gender and race perspective + the Public Authorities and society together

Leticia Sabino - SampaPé!, Brazil

GIS-based Suitability Analysis and App-based Smart Routing System to Enhance the Security for Women while Walking

Dr Andrea Gorrini - Fondazione Transform Transport ETS, Italy

Vivo Mi Calle. Living our streets.

Lina Quinones - Despacio, Colombia

The Walking In Schools (WISH Study): A study protocol for a clustered randomised controlled trial to evaluate the effectiveness of a peer-led school-based walking intervention in adolescent girls

Dr Leanne Doherty (nee Breslin) - Centre for Exercise Medicine, Physical Activity and Health, Sports and Exercise Sciences Research Institute, University of Ulster, United Kingdom

Session 3/2: First Principles for Engineers: putting pedestrians first

11am to 12:30pm, Room EQ-116, East Quad, TU Dublin Grangegorman campus

Description: Pedestrians are often top of our street design hierarchies, but they don't always come top of the list in street design. Learn how people-centered approaches to design can be achieved in a world where road design standards are still centered around vehicles.

Barriers to walking perceived by people don't necessarily correspond to those described in technical documents

Dr Tamara Bozovic - University of the West of England, United Kingdom

Reducing Pedestrian Delays at Signalised Junctions in Dublin

Oisín Devilly - Dublin City Council, Ireland

If you build it who will come? Exploring the effects of street improvements in walking behaviour

Paulo Cambra - U-Shift - Técnico Lisboa, University of Lisbon, Portugal

Get out of my Way! Or, politely put, understanding the nature of the 'barrier' in the review,

redesign and removal of redundant man-made structures on public rights of way

Rowena Macaulay - Walk Colchester, United Kingdom

High Visibility Crossing Places for Pedestrians

Dr Suzanne Meade - Transport Infrastructure Ireland

Session 3/3: City Policy and Planning Initiatives

11am to 12:30pm, Room EQ-112, East Quad, TU Dublin Grangegorman campus

Playback: [Session Recording Link](#)

Description: Walking in our cities happens by default, but not always by design. Around the world city administrations are making a conscious decision to give pedestrians priority - from Chennai to Rotterdam. Explore the key elements from funding to integrated planning and overcoming the challenges that city officials face.

Ghent: a cycling city that will become a walking city as well

Eveline van Hooijdonk - Mobility Department Ghent - team pedestrians, Belgium

Pedestrian on a pedestal. Where and why?

André De Wit - Municipality, City of Rotterdam, Netherlands

Austrian Klimaaktiv Mobil Action programme - Funding offensive for walking infrastructure of cities and regions

Robert Thaler - Federal Ministry for Climate Action, Environment, Energy, Mobility, Innovation and Technology, Austria

Session 3/4: Smarter than Smart: app., ethics & usefulness of data

11am to 12:30pm, Room EQ-211, East Quad, TU Dublin Grangegorman campus

Playback: [Session Recording Link](#)

Description: Learning from the data and building on session 2/5 this discussion will examine how we collect walking data, what different tools and approaches reveal about walking and

provide insights into how cities are using data for best impact.

Using machine learning and big data to discover what makes people actually walk in NSW

Nick Fletcher - Vivendi Consulting Pty Ltd, Australia

To walk or not to walk? Merging the walkability and walking accessibility concepts - the development of user-specific walking accessibility measures

Ulrike Jehle - Technical University of Munich, Germany

Walking Malta. An innovative Pedestrian-Centered Walkability Assessment

Carlos Cañas - Institute for Climate Change and Sustainable Development, University of Malta

Walking data - cities needs and market gaps

Marianne Weinreich - Ramboll Smart Mobility, Denmark

Envisaging a Digital Pedestrian Network in Singapore for Planning, Routing and More

Kankang Zhu - Land Transport Authority, Singapore

Session 3/5: Leveraging the Community

11am to 12:30pm, Room EQ-009, East Quad, TU Dublin Grangegorman campus

Playback: [Session Recording Link](#)

Description: This session will explore how communities can engage the power of local people to develop walking in their neighbourhoods. At all levels these initiatives reveal innovative projects and promotions that shed a light on walking and invite people to participate.

Walking Champions de Marche - leveraging Olympic race walkers to promote community-based walking initiatives

Dr Tim Berrett - Caminata Consulting, Canada

WalkRollMap.org: Crowdsourcing Barriers to Safe and Comfortable Places to Walk

Karen Laberee - University of Victoria, Canada

Project Force: getting your neighbourhood moving

Niels Linhart - Voetgangersbeweging VZW, Belgium

How to develop networks of pedestrian pathways in Wallonia?

Charlotte Angerand - Tous à Pied, Belgium

The first steps in understanding local and national level walking system in Ireland

Dylan Power - Centre for Health Behaviour Research, Waterford Institute of Technology, Ireland

Session 3/6: Pechas Kuchas

11am to 12:30pm, Room EQ-009, East Quad, TU Dublin Grangegorman campus

Playback: [Session Recording Link](#)

Description: Join a Pecha Kucha session to hear from a variety of projects in this dynamic, short-form presentation style.

Fortaleza Municipal Walkability Plan

Luciana Lobo - Municipal Secretariat for Urban Development and Environment of the Municipal Government of Fortaleza, Brazil

Transforming degraded land into Urban Micro Parks

Hannah Silva - Municipality of Fortaleza, Foundation of Science, Technology & Innovation, Brazil

Along Pilgrim Paths to Scherpenheuvel

Nina Van Meerbeeck - Interleuven, Belgium

Walk Which Way? Retrofitting Schools as Walking Destinations for Young Children and

Caregivers in Tirana, Albania

Simon Battisti - Qendra Marrëdhënie, Albania

Mapping, recognizing and rewarding projects which have expanded walkability

Louise Uchoa - SampaPé!, Brazil

Minecraft and Mobility: using Minecraft for community participation

Janene Tuniz - UN Habitat, Kenya

Mulranny Village Transformation

Pat Staunton - Mayo County Council, Ireland

Session 4/1: Making it Inclusive: walking for everybody!

4 to 5:30pm, Room EQ-002, East Quad, TU Dublin Grangegorman campus

Playback: [Session Recording Link](#)

Description: Walking is a mode of movement that is readily available and accessible for everyone, but inviting those more marginalised or hesitant to feel welcome requires understanding of our differences as well as our shared needs. With a variety of research and experience, this session will examine how we craft successful streets and spaces that work for, and invite everyone, to walk.

Walking For Everyone

Stephen Edwards - Living Streets, United Kingdom

Intergenerational Pedibus

Corine Kibora - Association Transports et Environnement, Switzerland

Woodlands for Health

Niamh Ní Chonghaile - Mental Health Ireland, Get Ireland Walking, Coillte, Ireland

Shared Space includes all people walking

Dr Pieter de Haan - Knowledge Center Shared Space, Netherlands

Session 4/2: Planning walkable neighbourhoods and developments

4 to 5:30pm, Room EQ-116, East Quad, TU Dublin Grangegorman campus

Playback: [Session Recording Link](#)

Description: Whether in Brazil or Botswana, the Netherlands or Norway, do the principles of good planning for walking remain the same? This session will elaborate on how we ensure walkability for urban regeneration or new housing programmes through these shared principles.

Linking Communities to Luas Light Rail

Sarah O' Donnell - Transport Infrastructure Ireland

Building parking-free neighbourhoods to encourage walking and active mobility

Emilie Roux - Association Transports et Environnement, Switzerland

Future Downtown Brainport – Eindhoven Knoop XL – a Place for People

Erik van Hal - City of Eindhoven, Netherlands

Promoting walking through central urban regeneration

Dr Maja Karoline Rynning - Institute of Transport Economics, Norway

Incorporating Walkability into municipal housing planning and development: Lisbon's

Affordable Renting Program

Paulo Cambra - U-Shift, Técnico Lisboa - University of Lisbon, Portugal

Session 4/3: Designing streetscapes that work for everyone

4 to 5:30pm, Room EQ-112, East Quad, TU Dublin Grangegorman campus

Playback: [Session Recording Link](#)

Description: The devil is in the detail for pedestrian facilities and this session gets to the heart of that detail. From benches to micro interventions and national guidelines, how we shape our streetscapes shapes the walking experience of everyone who uses it.

The Public bench – service station for pedestrians

Renate Albrecher - Ecole Polytechnic Fédéral de Lausanne, Switzerland

Beyond Tarmac: what communities really need to get them walking

Anne Docherty - Living Streets, United Kingdom

Sensing Spaces. How the senses influence the choices we make when we walk.

Alexandra Gomes - London School of Economics, LSE Cities, United Kingdom

How “open streets” are transforming public space in French cities

Pablo Carreras - Codra Conseil, France

From Monowalks to Winter Walks: Micro urban design measures in a winter city, for all age

groups and mobilities.

Prof. Francisco Alaniz Uribe - University of Calgary, Canada

Session 4/4: Talking the Walk: insights into how we think about walking

4 to 5:30pm, Room EQ-211, East Quad, TU Dublin Grangegorman campus

Playback: [Session Recording Link](#)

Description: We walk with our feet, but how much we value those feet is determined by our heads. This insightful session takes a fresh approach to the challenge of raising the status of walking and changing the way we think about something we take for granted.

Love Our Laneways: A Model for Engagement and Re-imagination

Aaron Copeland - A Playful City, Ireland

Trading off time, carbon, active travel, and health: what do people really think about traffic-reduction measures?

Dr Tom Cohen - Active Travel Academy, University of Westminster, United Kingdom

Rich Man, Poor Man, Beggar Man: Social Status Associations with Walking for Transport

Nadia Willia- Sustainable Transport & Mobility Research Group, Technological University

Dublin, Ireland

Results from the Dublin Walking and Cycling Index 2021 - formerly the Bike Life Report

Sarah McDonagh - National Transport Authority, Ireland

From niche to norm. How to make active mobility the norm?

Dr Sandra Wegener - University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences Vienna (BOKU),

Institute for Transport Studies, Austria

Session 4/5: Monitoring Impact: qualitative and quantitative data

4 to 5:30pm, Room EQ-009, East Quad, TU Dublin Grangegorman campus

Playback: [Session Recording Link](#)

Description: The final in our track on data, this session brings the results from key studies and interventions to examine the impact of health, environmental and behavioural interventions on walking activity. It also sets us up to ask: what does the data tell us about what to do next?

In search for the pedestrian. Steps towards the development of a pedestrian monitor

André De Wit – Municipality, City of Rotterdam, Netherlands

Walking fOR Health (WORTH) Study: reflections on the delivery of a feasibility randomised controlled trial of an intervention to increase physical activity and reduce sedentary behaviour in people with severe mental illness

Prof. Suzanne Mc Donough – Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland, Ireland

Learning from frequent walkers: motivations, practices, and spaces

Dr Farzaneh Bahrami – University of Groningen, Netherlands

The impact of the Community Made2Move Programme on Participants' Daily Steps

Dr Fiona Chambers – University College Cork, Ireland

How has Covid-19 impacted walking behaviours in Ireland?

Benny Cullen – Sport Ireland

Walkshops

Session 1/7: Walkshop

11am to 12:30pm

Healthy TU Dublin Heritage Trails & Walkshops

Dr Teresa Hurley – Technological University Dublin

Explore urban textures

Raphael Mak – Metrunner Sweden

Session 2/7: Walkshop

4pm to 5:30pm

Impact Storytelling & Youth Engagement with Pedestrian Dignity

Jonathon Stalls – Walking Artist, United States

Walking into Walkability Data: Exploring ways we assess and understand walking environments

Emmet Ó Briain – Technological University Dublin, Ireland

Orienteering Walkshop – How do we navigate in cities?

Raphael Mak – Metrunner, Sweden

Session 3/7: Walkshop

11am to 12:30pm

Every Step of the Way

Jim Walker – Walk21 Foundation, United Kingdom

Outdoor Navigation for People who are Blind or Vision Impaired: Experiences, Challenges and Future Directions

Chantelle Smith – National Council for the Blind in Ireland

The pedestrian experience assessment toward public transport stops with a pedestrian wayfinding approach

Yazmin Viramontes – CAMINA Centre for Pedestrian Mobility Studies, Mexico

Session 4/6: Walkshop

4 to 5:30pm

Talking nature in the city

Dr Ken Boyle – Technological University Dublin, Ireland

Walking the LIFELINE, a living laboratory connecting nature, people and place

Kaethe Burt-O'Dea – Desireland, Ireland

Roundtables

Thursday 22 September 2022

Roundtable: Prioritising walking and cycling in the mobility mix this decade

9 to 10am, TU Dublin Grangegorman campus

Jill Warren – European Cyclists’ Federation, Belgium

Roundtable: Handbooks to Transform Your Streets and Evaluate Them

9 to 10am, TU Dublin Grangegorman campus

Fabrizio Prati and Najwa Doughman – GDCl, United States

Roundtable: Transferring the ‘15-minute’ city principles to practice

9 to 10am, TU Dublin Grangegorman campus

Dr Luka Mladenovic and Dr Aljaž Plevnik – Urban Planning Institute of the Republic of Slovenia, Slovenia

Roundtable: Exploring the role of purposive sampling in engaged citizen science to enhance walkability in cities

9 to 10am, TU Dublin Grangegorman campus

David Buckley, Rachel Freeman, Dr Aoife Donnelly and Dr Tadhg MacIntyre – Technological University Dublin, Ireland

Roundtable: Change your Observation Focus: pedestrian counts: exchange of practices

9 to 10am, TU Dublin Grangegorman campus

Emilie Herssens – Walk.Brussels ONG, Belgium

Roundtable: Walkability Tools

9 to 10am, TU Dublin Grangegorman campus

Mario Alves – International Federation of Pedestrians, Portugal, and Dr Geert van Waeg – International Federation of Pedestrians, Belgium

Posters

Comparative Analysis of Pedestrian traffic volume and Quality of Street Space around Large Railway Stations Using Mobile Probe Data. Tomohito Nakai (Japan) – Osaka City University, Prof. Nagahiro Yoshida (Japan) – Osaka City University

The fresh streets of Sinaloa. Made for walking safely. Prof. Alejandra Leal (Mexico) – Céntrico, Prof. Xavier Treviño (Mexico) – Céntrico, Patricio Ruiz (Mexico) – Céntrico, Miguel A. Toscano (Mexico) – Refleacciona con responsabilidad A.C., Jaime López (Mexico) – Refleacciona con responsabilidad A.C.

Spring in Your Step: Turning Kildare parkrun green for positive ageing walk. Denise Croke (Ireland) – HSE, Daniel Russell (Ireland) – HSE

SNAILSTEP. Freyja Pérez Keller (Spain) – SNAILSTEP

JOÃO ALFREDO: from a street to a shared space for all. Ana Paula Hoppe Bonini (Brazil) – Municipality of Porto Alegre / Municipal Department of Urban Mobility, Fabiana Kruse (Brazil) – Municipality of Porto Alegre / Municipal Department of Urban Mobility

Pedestrian Mobility Appraisal in Mobility as a Service (MaaS): Exploring MaaS Solutions in the Paris Region Case. Mariana Reyes (France) – IRT SystemX and LGI, CentraleSupélec, Prof. Jakob Puchinger (France) – IRT SystemX and LGI, CentraleSupélec, Prof. Isabelle Nicolaï (France) – LGI, CentraleSupélec / Université Paris – Saclay, Dr Virginie Boutueil (France) – LVMT, ENPC-Université Gustave Eiffel

Schoolenvironment 2.0. Lieve Snoeckx (Belgium) – Voetgangersbeweging vzw

Notes on Walking: Dandelion has no Field. Jumana Hamdani (Sweden) – Architect and Lecturer, Sepa Sama (Sweden) – PhD Candidate on Walking

Making the walkable high streets: a planning support tool for Czech cities. Lenka Paszová (Czech Republic) - University of Ostrava, Dr Alexandr Nováček (Czech Republic) - University of Ostrava, Dr Ondřej Slach (Czech Republic) - University of Ostrava, Dr Vojtěch Bosák (Czech Republic) - University of Ostrava, Dr Aura Istrate (Ireland) - University College Dublin

Education should start early. John Davis (Ireland) - ITS Ireland

“Praia dos Namorados” Lakefront Revitalization Project. Vanessa Oliveira (Brazil) - Americana City Hall, Antonio Candido De Nadai (Brazil) - Americana City Hall

Analysis of Accessibility and Walkability to the main Public Facilities in the City of Fortaleza/ CE - Brazil. Leticia Costa (Brazil) - Universidade de Fortaleza - Unifor, Cristina Romcy (Brazil) - Universidade de Fortaleza - Unifor

Ville et marche au quotidien » a collaborative event devoted to everyday walking. Elin Lundmark (France) - Académie Des experts en Mobilités Actives (ADMA), Léa Devun (France) - Académie Des experts en Mobilités Actives (ADMA)

Walking and Cycling in the School Environment. Tessougue Temin Grégoire (Mali) - Friends Of Road for Mali

Luas Finglas Sarah O' Donnell (Ireland) - Transport Infrastructure Ireland

“Make Way for Pedestrians” – Some news of France. Anne Faure (France) - Place aux Piétons, Julie Berchoux (France) - Federaion Française de la randonnée, Frederic Brouet (France) - Fédération française de randonnée

The Wayfinding Centre - What if people with a disability led Public Transport design? Chantelle Smith (Ireland) - NCBI

Too young to die Maatla Energy Otsogile (Botswana) - society of road safety ambassadors, Galebowe Motlhajoe (Botswana) - Society of Road Safety Ambassadors (SORSA)

Visualization of Pedestrian Traffic Flow under Crowded Conditions on Urban Streets by Using Mobile Probe Data Prof. Nagahiro Yoshida (Japan) - Osaka City University, Naotaka Nishimura (Japan) - Osaka City University

Collecting and Modelling Pedestrian Movement Volume for City Planning Dr Yoav Lerman (Israel) - Planet Urban Consultancy, Yonatan Lebendiger (Israel) - Planet Urban Consultancy

Designing Walkable City in China in the Post-pandemic Era. Prof. Shengchuan Zhao (China) - Dalian University of Technology, Meng Liu (China) - Dalian University of Technology
Walkability as a potential for empowering women Lobna Galal (Egypt) - Department of Architecture-Faculty of Engineering-Cairo University

Walkability and Urban Public Health - Integrating Active Mobility, Built Environment and Health in Real-World Laboratories. Sina Diersch (Germany) - University of Duisburg-Essen, Institute of Mobility and Urban Planning, Kerstin Kopal (Germany) - University of Duisburg-Essen, Institute of Mobility and Urban Planning, Prof. Dirk Wittowsky (Germany) - University of Duisburg-Essen, Institute of Mobility and Urban Planning, Sara Klemm (Germany) - University of Duisburg-Essen, Institute of Mobility and Urban Planning

Small volume deliveries by foot and bicycle. Prof. Julio Cesar de Loureiro (Brazil) - Unigranrio/ Afya; Unyleya; SENAC/Fatec., Ione Andrade Loureiro (Brazil) - Unigranrio/ Afya, José Lobo (Brazil) - Transporte Ativo, Prof. Manuel Alexandre (Brazil) - SENAC/ Fatec, Prof. Rafael Deolindo (Brazil) - Unigranrio/ Afya, Prof. Koffi Amouzou (Brazil) - Unyleya

The 15-minute city concept - How can Innsbruck realize this goal? Silja Baumann (Austria) - Department of Geography, University of Innsbruck, Austria, Dr Rumana Sarker (Austria) - Unit of Intelligent Transport Systems, University of Innsbruck, Austria, Golam Morshed (Austria) - Unit of Intelligent Transport Systems, University of Innsbruck, Austria

The shortcut-map: an instrument for developing walkable neighbourhoods. Laura Nagels (Belgium) - Trage Wegen vzw, Pieter Vandenhoudt (Belgium) - Trage

A gamification-based intervention to encourage active travel. Dr Marc Harris (United Kingdom) - Intelligent Health, Dr William Bird (United Kingdom) - Intelligent Health

Private Landowners Training Programme in the Killarney National Park Biosphere Reserve. Dr Noel Doyle (Ireland) - Leave No Trace Ireland

Tactical Urbanism Workshop for Pedestrians as a Part of Good Design Izmir. Mustafa Gökberk Tektok (Turkey) - Pedestrians' Association - Yaya Derneği

Neighbourhood street redesign in small Slovenian town boosts walking. Mojca Balant (Slovenia) - Urban Planning Institute of the Republic of Slovenia.

An affordable, dedicated automated sidewalk scanner. Hendrik van Waeg (Belgium) - ignore the box, Dr Geert van Waeg (Belgium) - International Federation of Pedestrians

Do people with low back pain meet the physical activity guidelines: data from three walking trials. Prof. Suzanne Mc Donough (Ireland) - Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland, Prof. Deirdre Hurley (Ireland) - University College Dublin, Dr Paul Hendricks (United Kingdom) - University of Nottingham, Prof. Stephan Milosavljevic (Canada) - University of Saskatchewan

A study of pedestrian activity in a newly developed public space. Ahlam Alanbouri (Ireland) - tPOT Research Group, David Powell (Ireland) - tPOT Research Group, Dr Damon Berry (Ireland) - TU Dublin, Dr Lorraine D'Arcy (Ireland) - TU Dublin

The Future Design of Streets Dr Daniel Casas-Valle (Portugal) - Urban Dymics
ATOS Tool - the Grangegorman campus as a Case Study Kevin Burke (Ireland) - DBFL Consulting Engineers

The Benefits of Nordic Walking for Women Over 50 & People with Long Term Health Problems Joanne Burke (Ireland) - Nordic Fitness Ireland, Anthony Burke (Ireland) - Nordic Fitness Ireland

Walking in Africa - Understanding the barriers to walking for commuting Yana Tumakova (Germany) - Uni Kassel, Prof. Angela Francke (Germany) - University of Kassel, Azeb Tesfaye Legese (Ethiopia) - Mekelle University

Marquês do paran: rescue of the public space. Fabrcio Arriaga (Brazil) - Niteri City Hall, Renato Barandier (Brazil) - Niteri City Hall

Appendix D – World Café Consolidation

The World Café on Safety and Security when Walking took place as part of the Walk21 Ireland Conference at TU Dublin, Grangegorman on Thursday, 22 September. At its core was the concept of pedestrian safety. Delegates were asked to join one of three groups to discuss this in the realm of safety, equity and gender.

Below is a snapshot of three key elements from each topic.

Safety

It is important to differentiate between the perception of safety and actual safety.

1. The built environment should be designed with pedestrians in mind first, not last.
 - a. Design out cars
 - b. Accessibility and permeability
 - c. Benches
 - d. Surfaces suitable for winter weather
 - e. Avoid falls
 - f. Pedestrian crossing prioritisation with no more ‘beg’ buttons
 - g. Design in active travel
 - h. Lighting
 - i. Adequate footpath width
 - j. Maintenance of footpaths crucial
2. National legislation that prioritises pedestrians and controls drivers.
 - a. Car legislation change
 - b. Mobility legislation needed
 - c. Car taxation change, i.e. based on weight or horsepower
 - d. Reduction in vehicular speed
 - e. Policy requirements for active and sustainable travel to be built in to new developments

- f. Enforcement of existing laws, i.e. illegal parking on footpaths
- g. Ban car advertisements - lessons from anti-smoking lobby
- h. Public health perspective

3. Enough data not being collected and existing data being ignored.
 - a. Continuous improvement in data collection and communication needed
 - b. Always ask, “What is missing?”
 - c. Incremental knowledge development needed
 - d. Improved data for better understanding of safety
 - e. Data can feed mind and behaviour change

Equity

People working together is key to social equity.

1. Bottom-up approach
 - a. Community/People power
 - b. All needs addressed
 - c. Mapping areas better to understand existing barriers, i.e. lower socio-economic groups, rural townlands, access to and from schools
 - d. Address people’s needs from the bottom up
 - e. Community engagement events
 - f. Participatory action research
2. Social equity
 - a. Realistic alternative to cars - not everyone has access
 - b. Legislation for rights of way
 - c. Footpath audits
 - d. Rural options
 - e. Air quality

- f. Environmental justice
- g. Healthy options
- 3. Planning and design
 - a. Shortcuts
 - b. Desire lines
 - c. Crime prevention through environmental design (CPTED)
 - d. Not designing for cars
 - e. Smart mobility
 - f. Accommodating complex uses of the streets, i.e. traders on footpaths
 - g. Lighting
 - h. Eyes on the street
 - i. Public space connections

Gender

- 1. Women of all ages must be included in planning and design of spaces and delivery of infrastructure
 - a. Public amenities, i.e. toilets
 - b. Safety and security are door-to-door issues
 - c. Inter-agency cooperation needed
 - d. Make walking more Insta-friendly
 - e. Young girls and not considered in planning and design
 - f. Design for accessibility
 - g. Consider movement other than commuting
 - h. Post-occupancy evaluation
 - i. Broaden the view of transport beyond commuting
 - j. Embed design auditing with a gender perspective into design and delivery of infrastructure

- 2. Societal change needed
 - a. Awareness of women's needs required
 - b. Understanding of women's concerns and fears without victimisation
 - c. Educate professionals in design and planning
 - d. Social awareness and social sanctions for acts against women
 - e. Empowerment courses for girls and women
 - f. Support system to navigate transport systems
 - g. Make real and personal stories
 - h. Educate/Raise awareness
 - i. Empowerment through educational programmes for teens, young people
 - j. Women-friendly legislation - clear laws on harassment, equality of salaries/pay/job security
 - k. Guys following women in cars
 - l. Angry at women when not validated
 - m. Responsibility to de-escalate unwanted attention by men
 - n. Where do the girls go - "It's not our space"?
 - o. Walk less due to unwanted attention
- 3. Greater overall inclusivity
 - a. More women making decisions
 - b. Immigrant voices
 - c. LGBTQ community involvement - currently under attack
 - d. Inclusivity for people with disabilities both visible and invisible
 - e. Public space = shared space but how well is it shared?
 - f. Places to report issues
 - g. Non-gendered sports areas for all ages and with more diversity

Appendix E – Conference Feedback

Plenary 1 Feedback

The feedback for Plenary 1 was very good with 89% of respondents saying that the opening plenary was good, excellent or outstanding.

4. What did you think about Opening Plenary Session 1, Global Perspectives, National Commitment, Local Action: the research and political momentum for walking?:

	Poor	Fair	Good	Excellent	Outstanding	Responses
The session overall						
Count	3	6	30	41	8	88
Row %	3.4%	6.8%	34.1%	46.6%	9.1%	

Table 3: Conference feedback Plenary 1

Plenary 2 Feedback:

There was excellent feedback for this session with 90% of respondents reporting Plenary 2 as good, excellent or outstanding. The panel session had a lower satisfaction score with 78% of respondents rating the panel discussion at Plenary 2 as good, excellent or outstanding. Feedback given outlined that the short discussion time to explore the topic as a limitation. It was acknowledged that this could be seen as a limitation, but it was important to also show the relevance of the central topic to a diverse grouping in the short period of time available.

5. What did you think about Plenary Session 2, Walking as the foundation for healthy bodies, minds and streets?:

	Poor	Fair	Good	Excellent	Outstanding	Responses
The session overall						
Count	2	6	25	36	12	81
Row %	2.5%	7.4%	30.9%	44.4%	14.8%	
Panel Discussion						
Count	7	10	31	24	6	78
Row %	9.0%	12.8%	39.7%	30.8%	7.7%	

Table 4: Conference feedback Plenary 2

Plenary 3 Feedback:

“Great diversity of topics covered. Several excellent speakers who kept the interest throughout the presentation. Interview with Edith Toomey and her mom. This girl has a strong character and is a great speaker. Was emotional and strong!”

This plenary session had two of the speakers that delegates voted as being outstanding, Charles T. Brown of Arrested Development and the interview with Neasa Hourigan and Edith Toomey. 88% of respondents rated the overall Plenary 3 session as good, excellent or outstanding with 77% saying the same for the panel element of the session.

6. What did you think of Plenary Session 3, Ensuring equity and access for everyone?:

	Poor	Fair	Good	Excellent	Outstanding	Responses
The session overall						
Count	2	7	22	38	7	76
Row %	2.6%	9.2%	28.9%	50.0%	9.2%	
Panel Discussion						
Count	4	11	24	27	4	70
Row %	5.7%	15.7%	34.3%	38.6%	5.7%	

Table 5: Conference feedback Plenary 3

Plenary 4 Feedback:

Similar to other sessions with the majority of respondents rating the plenary session as good, excellent or outstanding (87%) with a lower number giving the same ratings to the panel discussions (74%).

7. What did you think of Plenary Session 4, Building for Walking: hard yards or easy street?:

	Poor	Fair	Good	Excellent	Outstanding	Responses
The session overall						
Count	4	6	28	29	7	74
Row %	5.4%	8.1%	37.8%	39.2%	9.5%	
Panel Discussion						
Count	6	11	24	29	3	73
Row %	8.2%	15.1%	32.9%	39.7%	4.1%	

Table 6: Conference feedback Plenary 4

World Café Feedback:

The delegate feedback for the World Café was mixed. While 82% of delegates reported it as good, excellent or outstanding, in the qualitative feedback reported that it felt a bit rushed.

“The World Cafe Groupwork felt a bit too rushed. I think future iterations would benefit from handing over a full day to workshops.”

World Cafe Groupwork						
Count	5	6	28	22	4	65
Row %	7.7%	9.2%	43.1%	33.8%	6.2%	
Consolidating the Conversation Panel						
Count	4	8	29	22	4	67
Row %	6.0%	11.9%	43.3%	32.8%	6.0%	

Table 7: Conference feedback World Café

Plenary 5 Feedback:

The feedback for this session showed that 93% of those that completed the evaluation found the closing plenary to be good, excellent or outstanding. The keynote speaker Skye Duncan of Global Designing Cities Initiative (GDCI) was also voted as one of the most impactful of the conference.

8. What did you think of the Closing Plenary, Walking Purposefully on Through the Decade for Change?:

	Poor	Fair	Good	Excellent	Outstanding	Responses
The session overall						
Count	2	3	24	31	8	68
Row %	2.9%	4.4%	35.3%	45.6%	11.8%	

Table 8: Conference feedback Plenary 5

Parallel, Roundtable and Poster Session Feedback:

Like the plenary sessions, the parallel sessions were generally well received and enjoyed. The majority of people were happy with the range and diversity of topics covered.

“The sessions had a great mix of presenters and it was great to have them all in one room conversing about their topics.”

10. How satisfied were you with the range of topics covered?

Figure 48: Conference feedback - Parallel, Roundtable and Poster Sessions:

12. The programme was designed to mix and showcase a diversity of topics and approaches to walking. In your opinion, did this?:

Table 9: Conference feedback - Parallel, Roundtable and Poster Sessions:

General Feedback

In the post conference evaluation survey respondents were asked to rate more general elements of the conference, such as a food and venues. Overall the response regarding these elements of the conference was very positive with all elements scoring well, the lowest of which was conference wayfinding, which was still at 70%. Delegates scored the helpfulness of staff, lunches and the Grangegorman venue the highest (satisfied and very satisfied).

28. How satisfied were you with the following elements of the event:

	Very dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Neutral	Satisfied	Very Satisfied	Responses
Lunches						
Count	0	2	6	31	43	82
Row %	0.0%	2.4%	7.3%	37.8%	52.4%	
Wayfinding						
Count	1	9	15	37	19	81
Row %	1.2%	11.1%	18.5%	45.7%	23.5%	
Helpfulness of staff						
Count	1	2	3	21	54	81
Row %	1.2%	2.5%	3.7%	25.9%	66.7%	
Programme information						
Count	0	10	9	37	26	82
Row %	0.0%	12.2%	11.0%	45.1%	31.7%	
EPIC Venue on Monday						
Count	0	4	7	25	28	64
Row %	0.0%	6.3%	10.9%	39.1%	43.8%	
TU Dublin venue Tuesday - Thursday						
Count	2	0	4	28	45	79
Row %	2.5%	0.0%	5.1%	35.4%	57.0%	

Table 10: General conference feedback

General Feedback Quotes

“That it was hybrid. I was only able to attend parts of the conference in person, but I could follow more sessions working from home while staying on top of work commitments.”

“Insights from international speakers (from outside Europe), programming (and having it easily accessible on the lanyard!), pleasant and comfortable venues (EPIC museum and TU Dublin campus).”

“The venue was perfect, walk-able to, from the city centre. The commitment from National Government departments was very refreshing and most welcomed, specifically the ministers who presented and the 20% Transport budget been allocated to walking and cycling demonstrates why Ireland will be a walking and cycling nation and an exemplar for other countries. I highlight Skye Duncan's contribution as a stand out and wrap up of the event and the Walk21 team, very slick in their operations.”

“Simply put: too many politicians. I understand that they may contribute a lot of money for the organisation of the conference and so they should have a platform, but none of them managed to inspire or excite me - quite the opposite. So much so that I - along with many other attendees - decided to skip the plenary sessions on Thursday. Another big issue for me was that there were hardly any slides. Please show us something to keep us awake, and to remind us of who is talking.”

“The venue (Tuesday and Wednesday) was great.”

“The Grangegorman campus, facilities and hosting.”

“The evening at the Mansion Room was a definite highlight. Loved the band and the food was superb.”

“The general atmosphere of the event was great.”

